

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

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1st Report on citizen's perception and concern: results of the surveys and focus groups

WP 3 – T3.2

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
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FROM
Chemicals

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version 3	10th March 2025	NA	Finalised document integrating feedback.

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Abstract

Most Europeans are concerned about exposure to chemicals in their daily lives and have doubts regarding the safety of various products. A recent cross-sectional observational qualitative study investigating Europeans' public concerns about chemicals emphasized the need for more accessible and understandable information for all citizens. Among its goals, PARC aims to gather more in-depth information about citizens' needs, perceptions, and concerns regarding chemicals and other related topics, and to develop targeted communication materials aimed at addressing these issues effectively.

As part of the PARC project, both focus groups and citizen surveys are being conducted in partner countries. In the first round of focus groups, Finland, Latvia, Portugal, and Sweden participated. Two focus groups were hosted in each country between May and July 2024. A predefined script guided semi-structured discussions, covering topics aligned with the study's objectives. Key topics included a brief presentation of PARC, sources of exposure, types of products of most concern, substances of concern, health concerns, preferred sources of information about chemicals, protective behaviors, and priority areas of research for PARC. The first round of focus groups provided valuable insights into citizens' perceptions regarding chemical use. Chemicals were perceived as both having benefits and posing risks to human health. Risks were identified at various levels due to their potential negative consequences. Specific contexts, such as workplaces, schools, and areas with higher exposure sources, were identified as having increased risk. However, it was also acknowledged that chemicals may offer benefits. Several groups were identified as being at greater risk. The primary exposure routes mentioned included inhalation, ingestion, direct contact (particularly through the skin), and exposure to rainwater runoff and inadequate waste management. Moreover, several potential protective measures at the individual level were highlighted. A recurring theme was the need for more accessible, reliable, and easy-to-understand information tailored to different target audiences. The discussion also emphasized the urgent need for stricter and more transparent regulations, along with effective enforcement, to better protect consumers from chemical-related risks. Further results at the country level and common themes that emerged from the eight focus groups are described in the deliverable. Additional focus groups will be launched in the coming years to provide a more comprehensive understanding.

The questions for the citizen survey were developed by reviewing previous surveys on citizens' perceptions and concerns about chemicals. The representative survey will be launched in the PARC countries in 2025.

By exploring citizens' awareness, concerns, and information needs, both the focus groups and the citizen survey will contribute to strengthening communication strategies within and beyond PARC.

Key Words

chemical exposure, health effects, citizen awareness, citizen survey, risk perception, risk communication, susceptible human sub-groups, focus group, qualitative data

Table of contents

Document history	3
Abstract	4
Key Words	4
Table of contents	5
Authors and Acknowledgements	6
Acronyms	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1 The “toxic threat” lifestyle - concerns about regular chemical exposure	8
1.2 “Intuitive” or “informed” toxicologists - perceptions and evaluations of chemical exposure risk	8
2. Focus groups with citizens: Methods	12
2.1 Training sessions	12
2.2 Participant selection and recruitment	12
2.3 Focus group structure and setting	13
2.4 Ethical considerations	13
2.5 Content analysis	14
3. Focus groups with citizens: Results	15
3.1 Finland	15
3.2 Latvia	19
3.3 Portugal	31
3.4 Sweden	48
3.5 Synthesis of the focus groups	56
4. Citizen survey	57
5. Conclusion	58
References	58

Authors and Acknowledgements

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Acronyms

CLP Classification, Labelling and Packaging

EU European Union

FIT Food Imitating Products

GHS Globally Harmonized System

USA United States of America

WHO World Health Organisation

1. Introduction

Never doubt that a small group of thoughtful, committed citizens can change the world; indeed, it's the only thing that ever has.

Margaret Mead

As citizens, we all have an obligation to intervene and become involved – it's the citizen who changes things

José Saramago

Chemicals, whether naturally occurring or manmade, are part of our daily lives (Prüss-Ustün *et al.*, 2011; European Commission, 2025a). While around 160 million chemicals exist nowadays, a relatively small number accounts for more than 99% of global chemical production (WHO, 2024). According to World Health Organization (WHO) reports, a limited number of chemicals for which data are available are estimated to cause 2 million deaths annually, attributed to a variety of health outcomes, including poisonings, heart diseases, chronic respiratory diseases or cancer (WHO, 2016a, 2021). This indicates that although the currently known disease burden associated with chemicals is significant, the unknown part may be considerably larger. The European Union (EU) already has one of the most comprehensive and protective regulatory frameworks for chemicals, supported by the most advanced knowledge base globally. In addition, the EU has been undeniably successful in creating an efficiently functioning internal market for chemicals, in reducing the risks to humans and the environment posed by certain hazardous chemicals, such as carcinogens and heavy metals, and in providing a predictable legislative framework for companies to operate in (EUR-Lex, 2020; European Commission, 2025a). However, the already widespread use of chemicals including in consumer products is expected to increase while the global chemicals production is expected to double by 2030 (European Commission, 2025b). Through its Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS), the EU envisages a number of measures including actions to support innovation for safe and sustainable chemicals, strengthening the protection of human health and the environment, simplifying and strengthening the legal framework on chemicals and building a comprehensive knowledge base to support evidence-based policy making (European Commission, 2025b). However, one of the most relevant challenges lies in the deficit of transparency regarding the chemical composition of products which may hinder the ability to assess the potential hazards and risks associated with chemical exposure (Molander and Cohen, 2012). Although certain achievements have been made regarding professional users, there remains room for improvement, especially in relation to regular consumers (European Chemicals Agency, 2024). Moreover, chemical pollution from products used daily can impact a range of facets of the ecosystems, which in turn also poses considerable long-term risks to human health as chemicals in these products remain in the environment for a long time. More specifically, the generation of total hazardous and non-hazardous waste in the chemical industry increased by 21% between 2012 and 2018, while in 2020 waste generation fell by 11% compared to 2018, most likely temporarily due to the COVID-19 pandemic (EEA, 2024b). The EU production and consumption of chemicals and downstream products can impact the environment and health, both within and outside Europe. Evidence shows that the planetary boundary for chemical pollution has been exceeded (EEA, 2024a). Therefore, chemical safety and waste management has become one of the priority areas of the European Commission which aims to reduce raw materials use in production processes and to generate less waste.

1.1 The “toxic threat” lifestyle - concerns about regular chemical exposure

During her lifetime, a person is exposed to thousands of complex mixtures. These substances can be found in food, soil, water, air, and dust, as well as in the products we buy and use. They are widely present in many of the products we use daily, including cosmetics (Rastogi et al., 1998; Barrett, 2005), household cleaning products (Rastogi et al., 2001; Gerster et al., 2014), gardening/agricultural and pests management products (Aktar, Sengupta and Chowdhury, 2009; Alavanja, 2009). They are present in the food and drinks we consume, including dairy products, processed meat products, refreshments and drinks, pasta, canned foods, and other long-life edible products (Loutfy et al., 2006; Khaniki, 2007; Cao, Popovic and Dabeka, 2023). Although it can be argued that chemicals are essential for the development of a modern society and that their use can bring substantial benefits and advantages, such as improved quality of life and hygienic and healthy surroundings (Calow, 2011), there are also negative effects, damaging our biological systems that cannot be neglected (Luca et al., 2018).

The European Union’s (EU) regulation on classification, labeling, and packaging (CLP Regulation) (European Commission, 2008) highlights the existence of many substances classified as hazardous in everyday products as regular ingredients (for example preservatives in washing and cleaning agents or heavy metals in electronic appliances). Many of these substances remain unnoticed by a relevant percentage of end-users who take the benefits of the chemical constituents for granted and trust that unwanted properties for man and the environment are negligible (Klaschka and Rother, 2013).

These topics represent, nevertheless, an issue of concern for EU citizens. According to the Special Eurobarometer 456: Chemical Safety, 65% of citizens from EU28 countries are “a little” or “very much” concerned about being exposed to chemicals in their daily lives, while 45% of the respondents felt well-informed about the potential dangers of chemicals included in consumer products. Regarding the perceptions on the safety of consumer products, 46% of the respondents expressed doubts regarding the safety of these products (EC DG Comm, 2017). Additionally, a recent cross-sectional observational qualitative study investigating the public concern of Europeans regarding chemicals emphasized the need for more accessible and understandable information for all citizens (Uhl et al., 2021; Matisãne et al., 2022).

Furthermore, this topic has become a subject of interest for policy-makers and industries as the unprincipled and incorrect use of these substances and not paying attention to chemical warning signs, in the long run, can cause a decrease in people’s performance and ability, a decrease in their quality of life, and an increase in accidents in the workplace (Mehrifar et al., 2023). This makes understanding components in the communication of risks from chemicals in daily use products a challenging and urgent issue (EEB, 2024).

1.2 “Intuitive” or “informed” toxicologists - perceptions and evaluations of chemical exposure risk

Today, individuals are expected to make informed choices. It is often assumed that such informed choices are based on adequate communication about risks to themselves or the environment, including when purchasing and using chemical products for daily use (Wieck, Olsson and Kümmerer, 2018). Also, in the words of Kraus et al. (1992), human beings have always been “intuitive toxicologists”, relying on their senses of sight, taste, and smell to detect harmful or unsafe exposure. Unfortunately, the limitations of this method have been regularly discussed, as studies have shown that consumers will likely not associate chemical products that they habitually use with risk, unless prompted to think about this (Buchmüller, Bearth and Siegrist, 2020). In fact, the risks perceived by toxicologists significantly differ from the general public assessment of potential chemical risks (Kraus, Malmfors and Slovic, 1992; Bearth, Saleh and Siegrist, 2019) due to perceptions being

influenced by several social factors as: education, social media environment, revenue, social status, urban or rural residence or geographic area, among other (Luca et al., 2018).

Every day, consumers are confronted with product advertising campaigns that tend to hinder their intentions to buy safe and healthy products. One interesting example is a study by Wieck (2015) that investigated whether German companies inform their customers extensively on the hazards posed by the use of disinfectants and promote only those uses for which disinfectants are considered necessary. Fourteen websites for different product lines of disinfectants were analyzed and the study found that while most of the companies followed legal requirements regarding advertisements, they still promoted their products for more uses than necessary while not giving a full overview of the hazards. This finding is particularly problematic since the risks and benefits of household chemicals often cannot be perceived directly, but people tend to rely on messages transmitted through marketing campaigns (Beck, 2017). However, another group of researchers was interested in whether consumers who are more educated and concerned about these risks can more successfully assess harmful chemicals in products (Hartmann and Klaschka, 2017). Through an online survey, they investigated the awareness of 1030 consumers whose' education level, knowledge of chemistry, and motivation were above society's average. The survey found that motivation, educational level, and chemical expertise did not provide an appropriate understanding of harmful substances in products. Therefore, the question is if well-informed consumers are not sufficiently capable of using risk information elements, then how much can be expected from the general public?

Previous research indicated that there are several shortcuts lay people use to determine a potential risk. For example, consumers considered that products manufactured in the European Union, products without hazard pictograms, products labeled as "natural", homeopathic products, or eco-friendly products would be safer than regular products (Bearth, Saleh and Siegrist, 2019). This probably reflects consumers' preference for natural products, as they believe that substances of natural origin cannot pose a risk to their health (Kahraman and Kazançoğlu, 2019). The understanding of these purchase intentions towards natural-claimed products lies in the trend that consuming natural products contributes to a sustainable and healthier life (Rozin et al., 2004). Hence, companies modified their communication strategies to claim that they produce natural products that are better for human health and the environment (Kahraman and Kazançoğlu, 2019). This gives consumers a subjective feeling of security, which is actually pseudo-safety, due to improper marketing and/or insufficient understanding. Furthermore, another existing risk factor is the ignorance of the dose-response relation. This means that substances generally considered to be safe can prove to be toxic if they are ingested in a large enough quantity (Saleh, Bearth and Siegrist, 2019).

In this sense, product marketing seems to be a key factor in confusing consumers (Schneider, 1977; Holbrook and Hirschman, 1982). This is because most people are influenced by product- and marketing-related factors in their purchase decision. For instance, product packaging is a well-known contributor to the experiential aspects of consumption (Holbrook and Hirschman, 1982).

A topic of specific concern is food imitating products (FIT) (Basso et al., 2014). These are household cleaners or personal care products that exhibit food attributes to enrich the consumption experience. These products, although not foodstuffs, possess a form, odor, color, appearance, packaging, labeling, volume, or size such that it is likely that consumers, especially children, will confuse them with foodstuffs and, in consequence, place them in their mouths, or suck or ingest them, which might be dangerous and cause for suffocation, poisoning, or the perforation or obstruction of the digestive tract (Council Directive 87/357/EEC of 25 June 1987, 1987). As revealed by many cases worldwide, such a marketing strategy led to unintentional self-poisoning and deaths (Basso et al., 2016). Both the USA and Europe experienced cases of accidental ingestions (some with lethal outcomes) due to "cleaners that look like beverages" (Miller et al., 2006; Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety, 2011). Further, if chemical household products are to be handled safely, knowledge of how a particular risk can be reduced is necessary to engage in safe behavior.

Therefore, risk communication provisions including hazard pictograms on the product containers, are established to aid consumers and workers in being aware of hazards and to implement suitable risk management behavior to minimize exposure and hence risk. The classification, labeling, and packaging of chemical substances and mixtures placed on the EU market is linked to the Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS) and is widely recognized as an effective tool to increase users' perception of the nature of chemicals and the extent of chemical hazards. Its goal is to provide an appropriate classification for chemicals according to their potential hazards and to convey essential information about these chemicals to users through standardized pictograms, signal words, hazard statements, and precautionary statements in labels and safety data sheets (UNECE, 2024). Additionally, the pictograms are complemented by hazard and precautionary statements that provide information about how to safely handle the product in question. However, this information is only valuable when appropriately considered by the user. A study on farm workers' interpretation of risk assessment data expressed as pictograms on pesticide labels, found that 50% or more of the study Interviewees had misleading, incorrect, and critically confused interpretations of the label pictograms (Rother, 2008). For example, the pictogram indicating a pesticide's toxicity specifying that boots must be worn, was interpreted as "dangerous to pedestrians" and "don't walk through pesticides". Another survey involving interviewees from some EU member countries suggests similar problems in understanding risk communication tools. The interviewees assumed that products like cleaning products (up to 9% of the Interviewees), paint (up to 10%), electronic appliances (up to 37%), or furniture (up to 38%) would not contain chemical substances at all (ECHA, 2013; Hartmann and Klaschka, 2017). Moreover, most personal care products contain hazardous ingredients, but current legislation in the EU does not require these to be labeled as hazardous products. Instead, ingredients must only be listed on containers to inform consumers of potential hazards, and it is left to the consumer to make their own risk assessment (Klaschka and Rother, 2013). A recent study on household chemical products suggested that only 1.8% of participants always read this information (Rezaei, Golbabaei and Behzadi, 2017). And for some products, such as furniture or electronic appliances, there is no legal need to inform about chemical ingredients at all. This raises the important question as to whether consumers' human rights are being violated by requiring consumers to make a risk judgment without the scientific background or level of literacy required for this task (Klaschka and Rother, 2013).

Finally, while risk communication tools are important, some consumers also rate less informative factors. These include affective experiences and the perceived effectiveness of the product. For example, a product may be assumed to be safe if bought from a familiar shop even though it is actually quite dangerous (Buchmüller, Bearth and Siegrist, 2020). Within the European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU), focus group discussions were conducted to gather data on EU citizens' perceptions of chemical exposure and human biomonitoring (Ganzleben *et al.*, 2017; Uhl *et al.*, 2021; Matisāne *et al.*, 2022). The results from all rounds indicated that while some participants demonstrated certain level of understanding of human biomonitoring, in general the majority showed a very high concern for food safety and the environment (Uhl *et al.*, 2021; Matisāne *et al.*, 2022). More specifically, focus group participants in the first round were aware of, and articulated general concern about, the potential uptake of chemicals through food consumption and/or drinking water, as well as the exposure from polluted air and water. The participants of the second round of the focus groups of the HBM4EU project were less aware and concerned about exposure through dermal absorption, when considering all uptake routes (inhalation, ingestion, dermal absorption) that are relevant, in general, for human biomonitoring (Matisāne *et al.*, 2022).

As the available relevant studies differ in their methods and findings about the consumers' perception of chemical risk exposure in particular, the objective of this study is to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by analyzing European citizens' perspectives and concerns about chemicals in daily used products. A more in-depth characterization of these consumers' perceptions may be further used to define the scientific

agenda in the area of chemical risk assessment, as well as to define health policies, with a view to the safe management of chemical substances and the protection of human health in Europe.

As part of the PARC project, both focus groups and citizen surveys will be carried out in the partner countries. This report only concerns the focus groups carried out in the first round (Finland, Latvia, Portugal, and Sweden) and the development of the citizen survey.

2. Focus groups with citizens: Methods

A qualitative approach was followed, with the study design following the principles of Grounded Theory and data collection through focus groups. As a qualitative research method, the focus group facilitates a structured discussion within a small group, involving the sharing and clarification of the participants' points of view and ideas. The focused conversation evolves around a specific topic, with the aim of collecting qualitative data (i.e. verbal and relational).

2.1 Training sessions

To ensure methodological consistency across all participating countries and facilitate comparability of results, two training sessions were organized with all research teams from the hosting institutions. The first session focused on the foundational aspects of conducting focus groups and data preparation (Appendix 1). Key topics included:

1. Principles of qualitative research approaches, providing an overview of their application in the study.
2. Sampling guidelines to standardize participants' selection criteria.
3. The focus group script, ensuring alignment with the study's objectives and thematic consistency.
4. Guidelines for conducting focus groups, including best practices for moderation and managing group dynamics.
5. Guidelines for transcription, covering standards to ensure accuracy and anonymization of data.

The second session centered on the content analysis of the collected data, covering coding techniques and the identification process of themes and categories, ensuring a comparable interpretation of the focus group discussions (Appendix 2).

2.2 Participant selection and recruitment

A purposive, non-probabilistic sampling approach was used to recruit focus groups participants to ensure heterogeneity regarding gender, age (18+ years), educational background, profession, place of living (rural/urban), and having children or not. The aim was to maximize the collection of diverse perspectives on chemical exposure. Recruitment methods included online advertisements on institutional homepages, social media, and public/community boards near the institutions responsible for hosting the focus groups. Additionally, individuals from previous studies (not necessarily focus groups) who had expressed interest in participating in further research were invited.

Exclusion criteria were established to focus on lay perspectives, excluding professionals with formal education or responsibilities in fields related to chemicals, risk assessment, or human biomonitoring (e.g., chemists, toxicologists, healthcare professionals). Other exclusion criteria were individuals unable to express themselves fluently in the language in which the focus group would be conducted or unwilling to provide informed consent. Volunteers gave their informed consent before their participation in the focus group.

Interested people were invited to take part in the focus groups either through face-to-face invitation, by email, or telephone. Before the focus group session, a detailed email with information about the study was sent to participants.

Monetary incentive was provided in Latvia, Portugal, and Sweden (a gift card - 20 Euros) for each participant of the focus groups.

2.3 Focus group structure and setting

Two focus groups were hosted in each country, between May and July 2024. Each focus group was facilitated by a moderator and a co-moderator with previous expertise in qualitative methods. The moderator and the co-moderator were professionals from the host institutions. Whenever possible, a notetaker was present in the sessions, to assist in capturing key aspects of the discussion not covered in the recording, to complement the primary data collection methods. A predefined script guided semi-structured discussions and included topics aligned with the study's objectives. The semi-structured format allowed an open-ended, participant-driven dialogue. The following main topics were:

1. Brief presentation of PARC
2. Sources of exposure (air, water, soil, products, food, ...)
3. Type of products that are of most concern
4. Substances of concern
5. Health concerns
6. Preferred sources of information about chemicals
7. Protective behaviours
8. Priority areas of research for PARC (suggestions for)

The sessions lasted from 60 to 90 minutes and, depending on the hosting country, were conducted in rooms at organizing institutions or online. In the case of in-person focus groups sessions, the seating arrangement was designed to encourage interaction, ensuring all participants could actively engage. In the cases of online participation, various softwares were used (e.g., Zoom in Latvia and Portugal). When online, participants were asked to keep their cameras and microphones on during the session to promote fluent participation. Participants of online discussions could also write comments in the chat during the sessions, which were later incorporated into the transcripts.

Verbal content was audio-recorded for transcription and analysis. Recordings were uploaded and kept on the internal protected servers of PARC project partners, taking into account the General Data Protection Rules (GDPR), and will be deleted according to the national requirements.

2.4 Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations followed the Declaration of Helsinki and applicable national legislation. Participation was voluntary, with individuals aged 18 or older eligible after providing informed consent. All participants were informed about the study's goals, data usage, confidentiality measures, potential risks and benefits, and participants' rights, including withdrawal at any stage, without repercussions.

Data protection measures were safeguarded, including pseudonymization of transcripts, with assignment of unique codes to each participant, and exclusion of identifiable information, such as workplace or affiliation when data were shared with the PARC 3.2 activity coordinators.

In all hosting countries, approval from the Ethics Committee was obtained before hosting the focus groups (Appendix 3). In Latvia, from the Ethics Committee of Rīga Stradiņš University, protocol No. 2-PĒK-4/357/2024, 15 April 2024. In Finland and Sweden, an ethics evaluation approval was signed according to Swedish law.

2.5 Content analysis

The focus group discussions were transcribed verbatim. The transcriptions were done in the language that was used during the discussions, including careful de-identification of all participants, and following predefined transcription guidelines (Appendix 4). Transcriptions were anonymized and analyzed using thematic analysis principles (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Each focus group participant utterance was set as the unit of significance for initial open coding. Two independent researchers per country collaboratively coded the data in four stages:

1. Initial coding: Assigning labels to text segments (units of significance) by two independent researchers
2. After completing the initial coding, MAXQDA 2024 IA® or other equivalent IA software assistant was used for uncovering additional codes (only done by the researchers using this software for analysis)
3. Theme development (axial coding): Identifying categories and dimensions emerging from the data and initial open codes
4. Reconciliation: Resolving inter-country discrepancies and consolidating a common code system for all the corpus (all transcriptions from all countries).

This process aimed to preserve essential content, develop manageable thematic summaries, and provide a robust foundation for subsequent data collection and analysis (from other countries for additional comparisons and interpretations).

The most relevant quotes for each code were marked in the original language (transcription) and translated afterward into English. After that, some quotes were selected to be included in this report to illustrate the participants' different perspectives.

3. Focus groups with citizens: Results

3.1 Finland

In Finland, a total of 11 people participated in the two focus groups (5 in the first focus group; 6 in the second focus group). The sociodemographic characterization of the participants is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Characterization of the participants (N=11).

Sociodemographic characteristics	N
Gender	
Male	2
Female	8
Other	1
Age	
35-54 years	6
55+ years	5
Educational level	
Non-higher degree	3
Higher degree	8
Having children	
Yes	7
No	4
Place of living	
Rural	1
Urban	10

The main themes emerging from the discussions were: 1. Sources of exposure, 2. Perspectives on the use of chemicals, 3. Information and literacy, 4. Health consequences of exposure, 5. Regulation, 6. Individual protection strategies, 7. Vulnerable groups, and 8. Chemicals. Each topic will be developed below, with the presentation of verbatims in Finnish followed by the English translation.

Sources of exposure

Sources of exposure were by far the richest topic of conversation in the first focus group, resulting in 25 different sub-categories. Food was the topic that particularly raised concerns among participants. Right in the beginning, the conversation steered toward the deteriorating quality of grain and food products and food product fakes (food fraud). "Shrinkflation" was the worrisome phenomenon that was mentioned. One of the participants was confident that the Finnish food does not contain excessive chemicals because the regulation works. Regarding food, traffic pollution in the vicinity of food production sites such as grain fields raised concerns among interviewees. The participants mentioned their examples of food-related chemical concerns, some of them making them laugh and some examples giving them shivers.

"jos syödään ruokaa, joka on tuotettu ulkomailla, niin eihän me voida oikeasti tietää sitä, että mitä kaikkea myrkkyä niissä on"

“if you eat food that is produced abroad, you cannot really know what toxins it includes” [female, 59 years old]

Similarly to the first focus group, the second focus group spent most of the time talking about sources of exposure. A couple of new sources of exposure appeared in the conversation. These are smoking, E-cigarettes, nicotine mouth pouches (popular in Finland), asphalt, dental fillings, apartments, and recreation sites built at former landfill areas, substances used in gardening, pollution from airplanes, cooking equipment, and indoor air quality.

The last theme has gotten relatively much publicity in Finland in recent years, and it has to do with microbe and mold that may cause different symptoms. Polluted outdoor air is another theme that has emerged. In short, the air in urban areas is considered more or less dirty, and by some participants shockingly so. On the contrary, the air in northern Finland is seen as almost not polluted at all.

One participant said that children are given too much medicine. Also, in the discussion children were seen as a vulnerable group to the chemicals. After discussing pharmaceuticals, also vaccination comes into discussion, and their potentially harmful effects are connected—though by one interviewee only—to children. In Helsinki, there are a couple of living areas that are built at former landfill sites, and one golf course as well, or at least this is how participants saw it, and some of them considered these areas as potentially harmful due to that. Building materials such as surface materials and vinyl floorings were seen as potentially harmful to human health, but this conversation covered building materials in general, too.

“Niin ja se että itekkin tiedän lapsia, jotka sairastuneet uusien kotien vuoksi astmaan ja heillä on jäänyt se sairaus vuosien päähänkin. Edelleen ovat astmaatikkoja”

“I know children who have got asthma in new homes they have moved into, and the asthma didn't go away, they still have it” [female, 36 years old]

Sanitary products were also seen as problematic by many participants. One of the related problems regards toxic sanitary products, such as dishwasher tablets. Another problem was the overuse of sanitary products such as disinfection, which leads to weakening immune defense. Pure drinking water (including groundwater reserves) was considered one of the gems of Finland, but some participants were doubtful that some chemicals might pollute that, too.

“Toi estrogeeni yleensäkin, kun sehän sitten päätyy tuonne vedenpuhdistamoihin, eikä se oo helpommasta päästä poistaa sit juomavedestä”

“estrogen, when it ends up into water treatment plants, it's not the easiest to remove from drinking water” [female, 50 years old]

Both focus groups discussed the clothes and other products people buy from Chinese web stores like Temu and Shein. Five participants expressed their worry that these products probably contain some hazardous chemicals. Around this theme, some participants shared eye contact and nodded their heads, as a sign of mutual understanding.

Perspectives on the use of chemicals

Perspectives on the use of chemicals were discussed from two viewpoints in the first focus group. First was how participants felt their own actions were too little to make a real difference on anything for the better. In relation to this apathic view, the idea of circular economy was put into doubt, because there was doubt if its processes can neutralize harmful chemicals at some point but instead keeps them in circulation. The other perspective was that there was nevertheless some improvement to the better in chemical safety. References to this were, for example, that there are professions where repetitive testing on chemicals is mandatory nowadays, and with a dark sense of humor, the nowadays banned lead cosmetics that poisoned people in Europe in the 18th century.

Information and literacy

When it comes to chemical-related information and literacy, sources of information spark a lot of conversation. Participants mentioned various reliable sources, which are the website of the local hospital, pharmacies, and web libraries, but also a web forum was mentioned. A couple of participants talked about shrinking font size in product information in packages, which makes reading them all the time more difficult.

“Sit EU vois määrää ne purkkien tuoteselostetekstit kooltaan hieman isommaks”

“The EU could demand a bit bigger font size into product information” [male, 65 years old]

The participants wished for more education and enlightenment about chemicals. This should occur in elementary schools, but also the public sector authorities could do more. Another significant theme in information and literacy was the “too complicated product information”. A couple of times it was mentioned that product information can be sometimes impossible to understand, which was ironically a very understandable concern.

In the second focus group, one of the participants suggested that authorities could establish a social media account dedicated to chemical safety issues. Also, radio and a “chemical correspondent” were mentioned as ideas to spread information about chemical safety. Also, in the second focus group, the insufficient product information and the issue of product information complexity were discussed. One of the emerging issues was food fraud—a topic that gains publicity every now and then—which can undermine the trust one can have towards the public authority who should be able to prevent adulterated food from entering the markets.

Health consequences of exposure

Various health consequences of exposure were discussed in the first focus group, some of which were related to food, some to the environment and some to pharmaceuticals like antibiotics and their overconsumption. Atopy, diabetes, and asthma were mentioned as chemical-related diseases, but their etiology was not discussed more than briefly or at all. The multitude of hormonal effects chemicals may cause to humans (and animals) was mentioned as well as a topic of concern.

Regulation

Another participant referred to the huge broiler chickens that are produced with growth hormones in America and is happy that in Europe it cannot be done (due to regulation). This feeling by the interviewee belongs to the theme of adequate regulation, which appeared three times throughout the focus group. In a nutshell, some participants were skeptical toward the capability of the regulation at national and EU levels but realized it manages to protect them from some toxic chemicals.

“Niin ja sithän ois tietysti syytä puuttua varmaan, niin ku sä sanoit, ison teollisuuden kemikaalien (päästöihin). Ei se kaivostoiminta oo ainoo”

“The pollution of big industries should be intervened; the mining industry is not the only one” [male, 65 years old]

Lack of regulation was another emerging theme in relation to regulation. Many participants would like to see more regulation on cosmetic procedures like lip filling, tattooing, and hair dying. They considered that many young people are ignoring the health-related aspects or are just unaware of any possible negative consequences. Participants wished that either the educational system or regulation would take some action to protect people from their lack of knowledge.

Individual protection strategies

Minimization of the use of chemicals and responsible consumer behavior were the two most discussed themes of individual protection strategies. The latter refers to the protection of nature as well. Discussed responsible consumer behavior is recycling plastics and other materials, favoring public transport, and responsible purchasing (favoring long-lasting good quality products).

Going to nature, use of natural cosmetics, seeking information, avoiding skin contact, not using herbicides, avoiding products that contain odorants or colorants, and avoiding foreign food emerged as new themes in individual protection strategies in the second focus group. In the theme of perspectives on the use of chemicals, the second focus group discussed that foreign countries are more polluted than Finland and that we are collectively culpable for transporting waste into developing countries. Some participants thought that humans pollute everything (with chemicals), and some commentaries see little hope regarding this human behavior.

Vulnerable groups

Vulnerable groups emerged as a minor theme and only in the second focus group. It is children who are considered to be most vulnerable to chemical hazards. Related to this, one participant stated that being afraid that some children among Roma people (referred to as Roma beggars) might have been exposed to hazardous chemicals while being in dirty environments, like landfills.

Chemicals

The chemicals and materials the first focus group discussed were microplastics, dusts, aluminium, herbicides, lead, and asbestos. In addition to individual chemicals, the co-effect of multiple chemicals worried some of the participants.

“Kun niis sanotaan, et turvallinen käyttöraja on se ja tää ja toi, mut sit ku niit tulee joka suunnasta, niin uskon semmoseen, et ne yhdessä sitte onki vähän niinku liikaa”

“When product information says a safe limit for the use is this and that, but when chemicals are all around me, I believe they together might be too much” [other gender, 38 years old]

In the second focus group, discussing the chemicals, plastics got attention as a diverse polluter, particularly microplastics. Participants mentioned various contexts and objects where plastics occur and dissolve into nature or into humans as well. A participant noted that us, humans, are now eating microplastics among food,

and that is not entirely avoidable anymore. Another participant mentioned that all buildings that “smell like new” contain very volatile organic compounds, which is a risk to people, for example to children in schools.

Brain fog, eye symptoms, dermal symptoms, difficulty to produce voice, shortness of breath (dyspnea), neurological symptoms in general, ADHD, tumors, and allergies appeared as new health consequences of exposure in the second focus group. Most of these were mentioned by one participant, but allergies were discussed by four participants.

To sum up, the participants in the first focus group expressed real interest in the worries presented by others and were considerably unanimous throughout the interview.

Similarly to the first group interview, the atmosphere in the second focus group was good, and participants used humor quite a lot, despite at times being a bit pessimistic or even apathic. After the focus groups, both groups continued their discussions on chemicals for a long time around a meal they were offered.

3.2 Latvia

A total of 19 people (12 in the first focus group; 7 in the second focus group) participated in the two focus groups in Latvia. The sociodemographic characterization of the participants is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Characterization of the participants (N=19).

Sociodemographic characteristics	N
Gender	
Male	7
Female	12
Age	
<35 years	9
35-54 years	8
55+ years	2
Educational level	
Non-higher degree	9
Higher degree	10
Having children	
Yes	11
No	8
Place of living	
Rural	7
Urban	12

The main themes emerging from the discussions were: 1. Changes in situation with chemicals over the last 20-30 years, 2. Routes of exposure, 3. Sources of exposure to chemicals, 4. Health consequences of exposure, 5. Aspects increasing exposure, 6. Vulnerable groups, 7. Individual protection strategies, 8. Problems related to information, 9. Sources of information, 10. Management strategies (at local, national and EU levels), and 11. Chemicals. Each topic will be developed below, with the presentation of verbatims in Latvian, followed by the English translation.

Changes in situation with chemicals over the last 20-30 years

There was a general consensus that the situation regarding chemicals has undergone some changes over the past 20–30 years. The deep concern of beekeepers about the effects of rapeseed fields on bees was expressed, with fears for their survival. Participants mentioned how organic farms face significant challenges when neighboring fields are treated with strong or banned substances, leading to direct harm to bees.

“Esmu dzirdējusi, ka bitenieki ļoti uztraucās par rapšu laukiem, ka bites varētu iet bojā.”

“I’ve heard beekeepers are very worried about rapeseed fields, fearing bees might die.” [female, 57 years old]

“Es lasīju par šiem, cik grūti ir bioloģiskajām saimniecībām, jo, piemēram, pastāv kaut kāda drava pļava no kuras bites iegūst medu, vai ir kaut kāda šī bioloģiskā saimniecība, bet, ja kaimiņš nomiglo ar kaut kādu stipro vai aizliegto vielu, tad attiecīgi tas ietekmē šīs te bites konkrēti arī kaut kādu šo citu kaimiņu lauku.”

“I read about how difficult it is for organic farms, for example, when there is a meadow or an apiary where bees collect honey, or there is an organic farm. If a neighbor sprays with some strong or banned substance, it directly affects the bees and also impacts the fields of other neighbors.” [female, 34 years old]

Another concern was related to the importance of transparent labeling on packaging so consumers can be aware of the product composition, including whether ingredients have chemicals or not. The expansion of the range of chemical substances was also discussed, and participants acknowledged the existing regulations and restrictions.

“... es nezinu, vai tas ir kaut kāds likums [vai cits normatīvais akts], ka uz visiem iepakojumiem jābūt uzrakstītam, kas tad ir sastāvā, kas tieši tur ir, lai patērētājam ir tiesības zināt, no kā tas ir taisīts, kas ir tā sastāvā un cik tas ir ķīmisks vai neķīmisks.”

“... I don’t know if it’s some law [or other regulatory act], but all packaging must have the contents written on it, stating exactly what is in it, so the consumer has the right to know what it is made of, what its composition is, and how chemical or non-chemical it is.” [female, 36 years old]

“Manuprāt, ķīmiskās vielas arī ir mainījušās, ka tās ķīmiskās vielas šobrīd ir plašāks klāsts, bet vienlaikus, tomēr atkal ir regulējums un ir arī ierobežojumi.”

“I think chemical substances have also changed, as there is now a wider range of chemical substances, but at the same time, there are regulations and restrictions.” [female, 48 years old]

There was a belief that access to information has significantly improved compared to the past — people are wiser — as more scientific data about chemicals (and their impacts) has been made publicly available. Additionally, the range of available products has grown, offering consumers more options with more natural compositions. And the chemicals are more accessible now.

“Mans viedoklis ir tāds, ka mainījies nav nekas, jo mēs esam palikuši gudrāki. Visticamākais, vairāk datu zinātniski pieejam lietām, līdz ar to mums ir vairāk informācijas par visu, salīdzinājumā ar padomju laikiem un mūsdienām.”

“My opinion is that nothing has changed because we have become wiser. Most likely, more scientific data is available on things, and as a result, we have more information about everything compared to Soviet times and the present day.” [male, 37 years old]

“Tagad visa informācija ir pieejama. Man liekas, ka tieši tā atbilde uz šo jautājumu - kas ir mainījies Latvijā ķīmisko vielu ziņā ir tas - ka cilvēkiem ir pieejama informācija par šīm ķīmiskajām vielām.”

“Now all the information is available. I think the answer to this question—what has changed in Latvia regarding chemical substances—is that people now have access to information about these chemical substances.” [female, 36 years old]

“Mums mūsdienās ar lielāku izvēles iespēja. Visticamāk, ir kaut kādas lietas, nezinu, kosmētiku mēs varam nopirkt par lielākām naudiņām, kur tomēr ir labāks sastāvs, dabīgāks.”

“Nowadays, we have more choices. Most likely, there are certain things—like cosmetics—that we can buy for a higher price, where the composition is better and more natural.” [female, 36 years old]

“Es domāju, ka uz doto brīdi mums jau visa tā ķīmija ir daudz pieejamāka, nekā tā bija kādreiz.”

“I think that at this point, all those chemicals are much more accessible to us than they used to be.” [female, 34 years old]

Indoors and out, a change has also been noticed. For example, attention to hygiene in the food sector has increased substantially. And rivers are thought of as less polluted now.

“Es esmu strādājusi par pavāri vairākās vietās. ... es zinu noteikti to, ka ir daudz vairāk uzmanība pievērsta bieži higiēnas lietām restorānos. Gatavošanas procesā daudz svarīgāk un daudz vairāk pārbauda to.”

“I have worked as a cook in several places. ... I definitely know that much more attention is now paid to hygiene in restaurants. It is much more important in the cooking process, and there are more inspections of it.” [female, 26 years old]

“Teiksim, es domāju, pirms 30 gadiem upes mums bija piesārņotākas nekā šobrīd.”

“Let’s say, I think 30 years ago, our rivers were more polluted than they are now.” [female, 48 years old]

Routes of exposure

Four main routes of exposure were identified by interviewees: breathing (paints, solvents, among others) despite the use of masks, eating, close/direct contact (through skin with proximity of air pollution but also by applying cosmetics and by wearing clothes), and drinking.

“Krāsas, kas ir ieelpotas, šķīdinātāji ...”

“Paints that are inhaled, solvents ...” [female, 48 years old]

“100 % viņi tur saelpojās gana daudz to visu, pat ar visām maskām.”

“100% they inhale quite a lot of it all, even with all the masks.” [male, 34 years old]

“Pārtika - tā būtu ķīmisko vielu grupa, kuru es tā ļoti nepārzinu, bet es ļoti labprāt to pārzinātu, ... jo tas ir tas, ko mēs uzņemam ikdienā, gan gribot, gan negribot.”

“Food—that would be a group of chemical substances that I don’t know much about, but I would really like to know more about it ... because it’s what we consume daily, whether we want to or not.” [female, 36 years old]

“Bet arī ir āda, caur kuru mēs arī varam ... uzņemt piesārņojumu. Kosmētika, ko mēs smērējam sev virsū ... Jā ... Arī caur to mēs uzņemam ķīmikālijas.”

“But there’s also the skin, through which we can absorb pollution as well. Cosmetics that we apply to ourselves ... Yes ... Through that, we also take in chemicals.” [female, 30 years old]

“Tieši domāju, ka tāpat mūsu drēbēs, visās gultās un visā pārējā ir tās vielas ... Mēs ar tiem visu laiku saskaramies.”

“I also think that in our clothes, in all the bedding, and everything else, there are those substances ... We are constantly in contact with them.” [female, 36 years old]

“Runājot par to, kam visvairāk pakļauts ... Protams, arī dzeramais ūdens iespējams ...”

“Speaking about what we are most exposed to... Of course, possibly drinking water as well ...” [female, 48 years old]

Sources of exposure to chemicals

Several sources of exposure to chemicals were discussed. Among the most frequently addressed were the food and the beverage industry, that use chemicals in excess and to alter the characteristics of the products. Food additives and supplements, and e-substances were also addressed. Personal care products/cosmetics, including women’s and children’s hygiene products were another mentioned source of exposure because of the popularity of cheap, low-quality cosmetics among teenagers which is often accompanied by a lack of information regarding their potential health effects, sometimes in the long-term. Household cleaning products were also identified as common sources of chemical exposure.

"Piekritīšu, ka pārtikas un dzērienu rūpniecība, kur tiek ļoti daudz izmantot šādas te ķīmiskās vielas, lai, manuprāt, nodrošinātu ilgākus derīguma termiņus, uzlabotu krāsu, garšu."

"I would agree that the food and beverage industry use a lot of such chemical substances, in my opinion, to ensure longer expiry dates, enhance color, and improve taste." [male, 36 years old]

"Tad arī dažādas miglošanas, kas notiek, kas, protams, ir kaut kāds tāds, manuprāt, ... pieļaujama un, kas ir tiešām absolūti nepieciešams. Bet šķiet, lai panāktu vēl labākus rezultātus, ražas un tā tālāk, tas jau par daudz tiek izmantots."

"Then there are various sprayings [of agricultural chemicals] that take place, which, of course, are, in my opinion ... permissible and truly necessary. But it seems that they are being used excessively to achieve even better results, like higher yields and so on." [female, 48 years old]

"Jā, par higiēnas precēm, piemēram, ziepes, šampūni, arī sievietēm kosmētika vai, piemēram, bērnu higiēnas produkti un krēmi, jo ir ļoti daudz arī sastāvā rakstīt tādas vielas, par ko īsti mēs arī neesam informēti līdz galam par šo vielu kaitīgumu ilgtermiņa lietošanā."

"Yes, regarding hygiene products, such as soaps, shampoos, cosmetics for women, or, for example, children's hygiene products and creams, because there are many substances listed in the ingredients that we are not fully informed about in terms of their long-term harmful effects." [female, 34 years old]

"Piemēram, iepriekš, kad es strādāju ar kaut kādiem skolēniem, jauniešiem, pieskaroties tēmai - daudzas pusaudžu meitenes sūta kosmētiku no AliExpress, jo tas ir lētāk, protams, nekā pirkt šeit, bet tā kvalitāte ir pilnīgi citāda. Tur uzreiz ir izsitumi, iekaisušas acis un tamlīdzīgi."

"For example, previously, when I worked with some students and young people, touching on this topic—many teenage girls order cosmetics from AliExpress because it's cheaper, of course, than buying it here, but the quality is completely different. It immediately causes breakouts, irritated eyes, and similar issues." [female, 34 years old]

"Varbūt vairāk ir tieši tad, bet kad dēls bija mazāks, tad es noteikti sāku vairāk domāt līdzī. Domāju, lai tā pārtika ir labāka, arī mazgāšanas līdzekļi ar mazāku ķīmisko sastāvu - bez smaržvielām un visu pārējo."

"Maybe it was more back then, but when my son was younger, I definitely started thinking more about it. I wanted the food to be better, and also cleaning products with less chemical content—without fragrances and all the other additives." [female, 35 years old]

"Tas, kas mani satrauc, ir arī uztura bagātinātāji. Liekas, ka viņi nav pietiekami regulēti, piemēram, nesen nopirku Spirulīnu, kur vispār nebija pat sastāvs rakstīts, tā kā Latvijas firma, bet ... tie uztura bagātinātāji ir tik plaši pieejami."

"Dietary supplements concern me. They seem not sufficiently regulated. For example, I recently bought Spirulina, and the composition wasn't even listed, even though it was a Latvian company. But ... these supplements are so widely available." [female, 30 years old]

“Jā, es varbūt no savas puses tikai varu izteikt tādu savu satraukumu kā mammai, kas ir jauniešu bērnu mamma. Divi gabali man ir viņi. Man arī pa visām šīm pārtikas lietām, kas mani satrauc, visas šīs E vielas, kuras tiek pievienotas ēdienam ...”

“Yes, perhaps I can just express my concern as a mother of young children—I have two of them. I’m also worried about all these food-related issues that concern me, all these E-numbers added to food...” [female, 51 years old]

Working with chemicals such as corrosive materials was another source of exposure mentioned as well as the importance of safety and protection measures and awareness in workplaces to avoid unnecessary exposure.

“Tīri darbs ar ķīmiju, kaut kādi korozīvi materiāli, ar ko būtu, tā kā vairāk jāpievērš uzmanība, tieši strādājot, lai maksimāli mazāk pakļaut sevi kaut kādam riskam.”

“Working directly with chemicals, such as corrosive materials, requires paying more attention, especially while working, to minimize exposure to any risks as much as possible.” [male, 36 years old]

Other referred sources of exposure included do-it-yourself activities (such as crop growing, repairs at home), clothes, exposure to environmentally contaminated air, proximity to industrial sources of contamination (either at home or the workplace), medication and insect repellents, salts, vapes, electronic cigarettes and smoking in general (including second-hand smoking) and proximity to environmentally contaminated water.

Health consequences of exposure

The most frequently mentioned health effects of exposure to chemicals were allergies and cancer, with consequences being emphasized for different populations. Immune system related diseases, skin problems, lung diseases, nervous system effects, eye problems, effects on liver and other internal organs, cardiovascular disorders and other unspecified long-term health effects and non-curable unspecified diseases were pointed out.

“Es varētu pateikt, ka mani uztrauc ķīmiskās vielas, kas ir pārtikas produktos, jo bērniem ir ļoti daudz alerģiju.”

“I could say that I’m concerned about the chemicals in food products because children have so many allergies.” [female, 57 years old]

“Mana draudzene, kas lieto dabīgās kosmētikas līdzekļus, teiksim, pastāstīja, ka izrādās, ka arī no dabīgās kosmētikas cilvēkiem var būt alerģiskas reakcijas vai dabīgās vielas, kas var būt arī stipras un spēcīgas.”

“My friend, who uses natural cosmetic products, told me that it turns out people can also have allergic reactions to natural cosmetics or natural substances, which can also be strong and potent.” [female, 34 years old]

“Nu jā, pārtikas produktos arī ir kaut kādas kancerogēnās vielas.”

“Well, yes, there are also some carcinogenic substances in food products.” [female, 48 years old]

“Laikam jau satraucos vienkārši apkārt klausoties, cik daudz tieši no vēža [mirst] ...”

“I guess I just get worried hearing all around how many people [die] from cancer ...” [female, 35 years old]

Aspects increasing exposure

Increased exposure was associated with two issues. First, personal attitude played an important role as a general reluctance or depreciation to adopt protective measures (i.e., wear a mask or gloves when handling paintings) can play a relevant role. Similarly, some people do not read food labels or pay attention to product composition.

“Jānokrāso sienas - neviens tak neliks mājās maskas un cimdus, jo tur var nokrāsot kaut vai vienu sienu ... “Ai, šoreiz nē” vai “Ej, nākamreiz”.”

“Painting walls—no one at home is going to wear masks or gloves, even if it’s just painting one wall ... “Oh, not this time,” or “I’ll do it next time.”” [male, 34 years old]

Second, lack of finances and willingness to allocate extra funds on protection measures was another verbalized aspect that can act as a barrier to adopt protection behaviors against (unnecessary) chemical exposure.

“Es vēl gribēju piebilst to, ka pie visām šīm ķīmiskajām lietām, kas notiek ar sienu krāsošana, tās lietas - aizsarglīdzekļus, tās maskas un cimdus un viss tas - viņi bieži vien ir jāpērk papildus. Tu vienkārši negribi tērēt naudu vēl papildus. Cilvēki vienkārši negrib tērēt naudu papildus visām tām vielām, kas jau maksāja.”

“I also wanted to add that with all these chemical-related things, like wall painting and such—the protective gear, masks, gloves, and all that—often you have to buy them separately. You just don’t want to spend extra money. People simply don’t want to spend additional money on top of what those substances already cost.” [female, 26 years old]

“... es kādu brīdi izmantoju aplikāciju, caur kuru pērkot kosmētiku, varēja noskenēt, kāda tur iekšā šī viela, pēc tam man apnika un tad bija jātaupa budžets.”

“... for a while, I used an app that allowed me to scan cosmetics to see what ingredients were inside, but then I got tired of it, and I also needed to save money.” [female, 34 years old]

Financial constraints and unwillingness to allocate extra funds for safety measures were significant barriers. For instance, apps to assess product ingredients can be appealing in the beginning but are often abandoned due to budgeting priorities or effort fatigue.

Vulnerable groups

Participants placed children as one of the groups at risk of chemical exposure, because of their unstable immune system. Persons with allergies or with deprived immunity are also more vulnerable. Interestingly, the role of genetics in more or less vulnerability was emphasized. The elderly population, pregnant women and persons with chronic diseases were other nominated populations.

Individual protection strategies

Participants emphasized choosing safer alternatives and minimizing the use of chemicals in daily routines as a protective strategy, through, for example, less frequent house cleaning or reduction of the use of unnecessary products, such as air fresheners. Prioritizing buying food from trusted, small-scale producers or growing own food were other protective measures suggested.

"...jo lietosim mazāk, jo mazāk ietekmē. Respektīvi, nevajag ikdienā, nezinu, mājas tīrīšana, uzkopšana, nevajag iet pēc definīcijas reglamentēts tīrīt katru dienu. Netīram katru dienu, tīram katru otro, katru trešo."

"... because the less we use, the less impact it has. Basically, there's no need to clean the house every day as a rule. We don't clean every day; we clean every other day or every third day." [male, 34 years old]

"Līdz ar to man liekas, viena no iespējām ir vienkārši lietot kaut ko mazāk, jo mēs mūsdienās esam diezgan pieraduši, ka mums ir viss kaut kas, bet realitātē bieži vien to visu nevajag ... [piemēram] gaisa atsvaidzinātāji."

"Therefore, I think one option is simply to use less, because nowadays we are quite used to having everything, but in reality, we often don't need it all ... [for example] air fresheners." [female, 35 years old]

"Es cenšos, cik ir iespēju robežās, dabūt, piemēram, tās oliņas no saviem paziņām, kuras audzē vistas vai kaut kā tā. Maizīti pārku maiznīcā, par kuru es zinu, kur strādā arī, piemēram, mani paziņas ..."

"I try, as much as possible, to get things like eggs from my acquaintances who raise chickens or something like that. I buy bread from a bakery I know, where, for example, my acquaintances also work ..." [female, 34 years old]

"Vispār cenšos pirkt Latvijā audzētus produktus, ražotus arī."

"In general, I try to buy products that are grown and produced in Latvia." [female, 64 years old]

In line with this, incorporating activities like regular visits to forests was seen as a proactive measure for maintaining health.

"... vismaz reizi nedēļā aizbraukt uz mežu, tas ir veselīgi."

"...at least going to the forest once a week, it's healthy." [female, 36 years old]

The use of digital solutions such as apps to check the ingredients in products was seen as a way to make informed choices.

"Es vēl varētu pieminēt par to, ka es kādu brīdi izmantoju aplikāciju, caur kuru pārku kosmētiku, varēja noskenēt, kāda tur iekšā šī viela..."

"I could also mention that for a while, I used an app where, when buying cosmetics, I could scan to see what ingredients were inside..." [female, 34 years old]

Problems related to information

While access to reliable information was an emergent topic throughout the conversation, several problems were identified. The first relates to the spread of untrustworthy and misleading information, namely in labels, television, and mass media.

"Tajā pašā laikā arī ekoloģiskā pārtika var nebūt ekoloģiska, jo ... kāda darba kolēģe man stāstīja, ka viņa ir bijusi uz robežas, kur redzējusi, kur tiek šīs [Eco] uzlīmītes pārlīmētas. Nu, jā, ir daudz viltus un melīga informācija."

"At the same time, organic food might not actually be organic, because... a colleague of mine told me that she had been to the border where she saw these [Eco] labels being re-sticked. So yes, there's a lot of false and misleading information." [female, 57 years old]

"Es neuzticos, ne televīzijai, nemaz medijiem, ne ziņām, ne nekādam ... Ja man ir kaut kāds jautājums, tad es griežos tieši pie speciālista, kas strādā tajā jomā, ne masu medijos."

"I don't trust television, the media, the news, or anything like that... If I have a question, I turn directly to a specialist who works in that field, not to mass media." [female, 30 years old]

Interviewees also mentioned having difficulties reading and understanding labels and information available in products due to the use of technical details, the availability of the information in languages other than Latvian, or just because people live in a rush and do not have time. Although the internet has been used to overcome these struggles, low digital skills and access to the internet can be a barrier to access information.

"Man laikam ļoti vājas zināšanas tajā visā būs, jo tāpat, lasot uz tiem produktiem vai vienalga uz kādām etiķetēm, pēc tam jāsež ilgi Googlē un jāsaprot, kas tas ir, kam viņš ir domāts, kas un kā utt."

"I probably have very little knowledge about all this because even when reading labels on products or anything else, I still have to spend a long time on Google to understand what it is, what it's meant for, and so on." [male, 34 years old]

"Piemēram, uz saldā sieriņa [populārs vietējā ražojuma saldaiss piens produkts] ir uzrakstītas visādas, tās E vielas un pārējās vielas, bet, ja vajadzētu pilnīgi visas ķīmiskās vielas uzrakstīt, tad tam papīram būtu jāiet piecreiz apkārt pārtikas mazajiem produktiņam, tā kā viss tur nav uzrakstīts."

"For example, on a sweet cheese [a popular local dairy dessert], all sorts of E-numbers and other substances are listed, but if they had to write down every single chemical, the label would need to wrap around the small food item five times. So not everything is listed there." [female, 57 years old]

“Veikalā, droši vien es lasu - daļu saprotu, daļa nesaprotu, bet ļoti neiedziļinos. Ja tajā ikdienas steigā - ja man garšos, ja man patīks - tad es pirkšu.”

“In the store, I probably read the label—some of it I understand, some I don’t, but I don’t go into much detail. In the rush of daily life, if I like the taste and I enjoy it, then I’ll buy it.” [female, 34 years old]

Participants highlighted the prevalence of misleading marketing practices that promote products as healthier than they truly are.

“Visvairāk es esmu pakļauta ... mārketinga trikiem vai melīgai informācijai, jo, piemēram, aizejot uz kādu veikalu, tur ir rakstīts “svaiga, veselīga gaļa”, bet tad es noskatos dokumentālo filmu, ka no veselīgas gaļas, tur ir ļoti maz, jo lopi tiek baroti ar tādu ķīmiju, lai viņi izaugtu, nevis sešos mēnešos, bet trīs.”

“I’m mostly exposed to ... marketing tricks or misleading information. For example, when I go to a store and see “fresh, healthy meat” written, but then I watch a documentary and realize there’s very little that’s healthy about it because the animals are fed with chemicals to make them grow not in six months, but in three.” [female, 57 years old]

A gap in terms of transparency across consumer goods was also highlighted, since, while food tends to have more detailed information on labels, other areas of potential chemical exposure with important potential health consequences, such as clothing, are often overlooked.

“Piemēram, uz pārtikas produktiem mēs izlasām kaut cik kaut kādam produktam etiķetes, kā tiek apstrādāti, vai kas atrodas šajā produktu sastāvā. Piemēram, apģērbu mēs nesekosim līdzī, ar kādām vielām tas tiek apstrādāts, krāsots vai balināts un ... tas ir ciešā saskarē 24/7 ar mūsu ādu un par to mēs neesam informēti, kā tas ietekmē mūsu organismu, imūnsistēmu un visu darbību.”

“For example, with food products, we might read the labels to some extent to see how they are processed or what’s in their composition. But with clothing, we don’t follow up on what substances it’s treated, dyed, or bleached with ... and it’s in close contact with our skin 24/7. We’re not informed about how this affects our body, immune system, and overall functioning.” [female, 34 years old]

Sources of information

Citizens discussed various sources of chemical exposure. The most trustworthy sources were experts (e.g., doctors, chemistry professors, state institutions, and universities) as they placed credibility on the disseminated information. Information from producers (e.g., labels, packaging, technical information, material safety sheets, and producers' websites) was also deemed as reliable sources.

“Manuprāt, tam ..., kas to stāsta jābūt ekspertiem. Piemēram, ārstiem vai ... ķīmijas profesoriem, vēl kaut kam, tā kā tiešām sabiedrības uzticamiem cilvēkiem, ekspertiem par tieši šo jomu.”

“In my opinion, those who present this information ... should be experts. For example, doctors or ... chemistry professors, or others—truly trustworthy people in society who are experts specifically in this field.” [female, 36 years old]

“Lasu tās pašas tehniskās datu lapas par ķīmisko vielu, kas ir produktiem vai precēm vai nezinu, nopērkamas veikalā ... Tāpat tā pati krāsošana, palasi un apskaties to tehnisko datu lapu, kādas ķīmiskās vielas tur iekšā.”

“I read those same technical data sheets about the chemical substances in products or goods, or whatever is available in the store... For example, with painting, you read and look at the technical data sheet to see what chemical substances are in it.” [male, 37 years old]

Other sources of information mentioned include: the internet (Google and Wikipedia), documentaries, broadcast on television, in libraries and in small towns, media, both traditional and online articles, social media (namely through Youtube and influencers), friends, family, and other relatives who have used or experimented certain chemicals.

Participants emphasized the importance of promoting awareness campaigns to inform the general public and of disseminating information in Latvian to be effective.

“Respektīvi, ja skatāmies Eiropas kontekstā, tad kā labāk informēt? Droši vien, ka kampaņveidā, tas viss būtu saistīts droši vien labāk ar pētījumiem - klīniskiem, neklīniskiem vai attiecīgi organizētiem, kur ir respektīvi kaut kāds rezonējošs secinājums.”

“In other words, if we look at it in the European context, how to better inform people? Probably through campaigns, which would ideally be linked to research—clinical, non-clinical, or appropriately organized—that provides some kind of resonating conclusion.” [male, 37 years old]

Management strategies (at local, national, and EU levels),

Various management strategies to address chemical exposure were discussed, with research, regulation, education, and better planning being highlighted as priorities. In terms of research, the importance of undertaking more studies on both high- and low-risk chemicals was stressed. State institutions were considered critical in supervising imported goods, guaranteeing product safety, and disseminating information to the public about harmful substances. Integrating chemical education (product composition, usage impacts, and comparative product analysis) into the school curriculum was seen as a long-term solution.

“Jā, viennozīmīgi pētījumi jāveic. Tieši kādu ķīmisko vielu jomā? Droši vien jebkuru, sākot jau no tā riska faktora. Spektrs ir ļoti liels, sākot ar zema riska un beidzot ar visaugstākā. Droši vien pastiprinātu uzmanību vajadzētu pievērst šīm augsta riska ķīmiskajām vielām, un nedrīkst aizmirst arī par zema riska.”

“Yes, research definitely needs to be conducted. In which area of chemical substances? Probably any, starting with risk factors. The spectrum is very broad, ranging from low-risk to the highest-risk substances. Increased attention should probably be paid to these high-risk chemical substances, but low-risk ones shouldn't be forgotten either.” [male, 36 years old]

“Jā, man laikam patiktu, ka nevis es tur tagad lasu cauri, visas tās E vielas un tā, bet būtu kāda valsts iestāde, tāda uzticama, ... un norādītu, ka – jā, šis produkts ir drošs.”

“Yes, I think I would prefer not having to go through and read all those E-numbers myself, but rather that there would be a trustworthy state institution ... that would indicate, “Yes, this product is safe.”” [female, 48 years old]

“Vairāk pārbaudīt lieltirgotājus, kas ievēd no citām valstīm, piemēram, saldumus.”

“Conduct more checks on large distributors who import products from other countries, for example, sweets.” [female, 57 years old]

“Daudz ko var pārnest arī uz skolām, tieši mācību priekšmetos, lai skaidrotu ietekmi un ilgtermiņā, tas, ko viņi ikdienā jau izmanto, ko pieliek, un kas tur ir iekšā.”

“Much of this can also be incorporated into schools, specifically in subjects, to explain the impact and, in the long term, what they use daily, what they apply, and what is inside those products.” [female, 34 years old]

Lobbying was identified as a significant barrier to progress in chemical management and regulatory actions. At the municipal level, planning improvements were considered necessary to avoid harmful chemical exposure. Careful placement of factories away from residential areas was also advocated as crucial. Finally, simplifying bureaucracy for small-scale producers was seen as an alternative to simplify bureaucracies and encourage eco-friendly and local farming practices.

“Tur jau baigais risks, ja norisinās kaut kāda lobēšana kaut kādiem produktiem, un vēl kaut kas.”

“There’s a big risk if lobbying for certain products or something similar occurs.” [female, 48 years old]

“Pašvaldības ziņā, es domāju, ka ... pašvaldībai būtu jāpadomā vairāk, kur būvēt tās rūpnīcas, vispārējās ražotnes centies nebūvēt tuvu dzīvojamajiem rajoniem, tas arī ietekmētu pozitīvā ziņā. Citreiz izskatās, ka viss ir sajucis kopā, tur ir ražošanas, tur pat ir tie mazie ciematiņi un tur dzīvokļu mājas, tā kaut kādā ziņā.”

“On the municipal level, I think that ... the municipality should think more carefully about where to build factories and general production facilities, trying not to place them too close to residential areas, as that would have a positive impact. Sometimes it seems like everything is mixed together—there’s production, small villages, and apartment buildings all in the same area.” [male, 41 years old]

“Valsts varētu vairāk atbalstīt mūsu mājražotājus vai mazumtirgotājus. Atbalstīt tādā ziņā, ka varētu uz pusi samazināt to milzīgo birokrātiju, lai viena tante var pārdot oliņas, lai viens onkulis var ķiplokus izaudzēt un viņam nebūtu tie bezgalīgie papīri.”

“The state could provide more support to our small-scale producers or retailers. Support in the sense of reducing the massive bureaucracy by half, so that one aunt can sell eggs, and one uncle can grow garlic without endless paperwork.” [female, 57 years old]

Chemicals

During the discussion, different chemicals were nominated by the interviewees, including food contaminants, as additives and palm oil, environmental pollutants, namely microplastics, pesticides, herbicides, heavy metals, and coal dust, household chemicals, such as washing powder, paints, solvents, and fluorine, industrial substances as asphalt, and chemicals present in personal care products such as laureth sulfate and aluminum.

3.3 Portugal

In Portugal, a total of 20 people participated in the two focus groups (9 in the first focus group; 11 in the second focus group). The sociodemographic characterization of the participants is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Characterization of the participants (N=20).

Sociodemographic characteristics	N
Gender	
Male	3
Female	17
Age	
<35 years	6
35-54 years	7
55+ years	7
Educational level	
Non-higher degree	7
Higher degree	13
Having children	
Yes	9
No	11
Place of living	
Rural	8
Urban	12

The main themes emerging from the discussions were: 1. Sources of exposure, 2. Perspectives on the use of chemicals, 3. Information and literacy, 4. Health consequences of exposure, 5. Regulation, 6. Individual protection strategies, 7. Contexts of (increased) risk, 8. Vulnerable groups, 9. Pathways of exposure and 10. Chemicals. Each topic will be developed below, with the presentation of verbatims in Portuguese, followed by the English translation.

Sources of exposure

Participants expressed several concerns about sources of chemical exposure in everyday life. Food emerged as a primary concern, namely about pesticides and herbicides used in agriculture. According to some participants, these chemicals can contaminate fruits, vegetables, and even water (rivers and sea) which, in turn, can affect the animals we eat.

“Preocupa-me muito as do ar, as que andam em partículas no ar e as que nós ingerimos diariamente quando nos alimentamos. Quer nos alimentos verdes, crus, quer nos peixes e carnes principalmente. Mas hoje em dia acho que estamos a ter muita poluição, não só de químicos, mas nos peixes, que acaba por ser uma prática preocupante e assim como nos vegetais, não é? Tudo isso acaba por prejudicar a nossa saúde e causar vários danos às nossas células e órgãos e por aí vai.”

“I’m very concerned about air pollution, the particles in the air and the ones we ingest daily through our food. Whether it’s in fresh, raw greens, or mainly in fish and meat. But nowadays, I think we’re facing a lot of pollution—not just from chemicals but also in fish—which ends up being a worrying issue, as it is

with vegetables, right? All of this ultimately harms our health, causing various damages to our cells and organs, and so on.” [female, 56 years old]

“Exato, ou seja, toda a alimentação, mas neste caso a fruta e os legumes, que é a coisa mais pura que nós podemos comprar e que, na verdade, vem cheia de porcarias e coisas que podem até provocar doenças graves.”

“Exactly, that is, all types of food, but in this case, fruit and vegetables, which are the purest things we can buy and yet, in reality, are full of harmful substances that can even cause serious illnesses.” [female, 31 years old]

Food preparation was also identified as an important yet often overlooked source of chemical exposure. This includes, for example, the high temperature frying methods used in fast food potatoes, as well as the use of inappropriate cooking appliances.

Household cleaning products were also mentioned as a potentially problematic source of exposure. Skin and respiratory effects reflect the need to use more natural cleaning products. However, the importance of using chemical products in certain situations was acknowledged and considered beneficial.

“Sim, desligar o chip de que, por exemplo, na limpeza da casa, que tem que ser tudo limpo no mínimo espaço de tempo. Isso também leva a que os comerciantes e tudo mais coloquem mais químicos nos produtos. Se eu pensar, ok, em vez de demorar 5 minutos, vou demorar 10, mas vai ficar igualmente limpo, posso utilizar... Escolho utilizar um produto que tenha menos carga química, não é? Por isso... É isso. Essas coisas, pelo menos, faço.”

“Yes, disconnecting from the mindset that, for example, when cleaning the house, everything has to be spotless in the shortest time possible. That also leads merchants and others to put more chemicals in their products. If I think, okay, instead of taking 5 minutes, I’ll take 10, but it will still be just as clean, I can choose to use a product with less chemical load, right? So... That’s it. Those are the kinds of things I at least try to do.” [female, 28 years old]

Domestic pest control substances were also highlighted, with one participant expressing surprise at the easy accessibility of strong poisons in supermarkets. Air pollution was another identified source, both in environmental terms (from smoke and dust emitted by factory chimneys to suspended particles from airports) and in workplaces, for example, because of the continued use of air conditioning. This presence of chemicals in working settings was addressed at other levels. One participant shared her experience with handling chemicals in a laboratory which requires personal protective equipment, while another expressed concern about her partner’s exposure to toluene in a paper factory, linking it to fertility issues. Another participant mentioned the prolonged exposure of healthcare professionals to radiation during tomography procedures.

“Na minha profissão [enfermagem], nós temos muitos produtos que no dia-a-dia nós contactamos e estamos constantemente a correr riscos.”

“In my profession [nursing], we deal with many products on a daily basis, and we are constantly exposed to risks.” [male, 63 years old]

“Ainda relativamente à questão dos empregos. [...] o meu companheiro, no caso, trabalha numa fábrica de papel medicinal, certamente vocês conhecem, é quando abrem as compressas e tudo mais, aquele papel com o plástico. Ele trabalha numa fábrica que corta e imprime esse papel e há uma substância química à qual ele está extremamente exposto, que é o tolueno, é o toluol também. E o que também é coincidência muito estranha é que todas as mulheres que trabalham naquela fábrica, nunca nenhuma delas conseguiu ter filhos.”

“Regarding the issue of jobs, [...] my partner, for instance, works in a medical paper factory—you’re probably familiar with it, it’s the paper with plastic used when opening compresses and similar items. He works in a factory that cuts and prints this paper, and there’s a chemical substance he’s extremely exposed to, which is toluene, or toluol. What’s also a very strange coincidence is that none of the women who work in that factory have ever been able to have children.” [female, 28 years old]

Personal care products were also discussed, with several participants referring to the presence of chemicals in shampoos, creams, and hair dyes. The absorption of chemicals through the scalp from hair dye and the recommendation to avoid the use of certain hair products during pregnancy were debated.

Other sources of exposure addressed included asbestos in schools, smoke, medical drugs and devices, contaminated water with heavy metals, paint for house repair, ink from books, hospital waste, electrical batteries, and mining activities.

Perspectives on the use of chemicals

Participants presented two opposing perspectives on the use of chemicals, one more related to benefits and the other one regarding concerns and barriers.

In terms of **benefits**, the critical role of chemicals in improving health outcomes (for example, for chronic diseases and life-threatening conditions like cancer) was emphasized.

“E há químicos que são importantes e que são bons, e que são importantes para nós. Até mesmo medicamentos analgésicos.”

“And there are chemicals that are important and that are good, and that are important to us. Even painkillers.” [male, 57 years old]

“Acabam por surgir problemas oncológicos que têm que ser tratados com produtos químicos.”

“You end up with oncological problems that have to be treated with chemicals.” [female, 28 years old]

Some participants also noted the progress in sustainable agricultural practices and in using chemicals to ensure the safety of drinking water.

Sim, mas hoje em dia nós temos várias maneiras de fazer cultivo, com menor uso de água e com práticas mais sustentáveis.

“Yes, but nowadays we have several ways of growing crops, with less use of water and more sustainable practices.” [female, 28 years old]

“Mas a água de consumo tem que ser colocados lá químicos para garantir que já há consumo.”

“But the drinking water has to have chemicals added to it to ensure that it is already consumed.” [female 25 years old]

On the other hand, citizens expressed several **concerns** regarding the potential risks associated with chemical exposure. First, some addressed the lack of information available about the use of chemicals in everyday products, such as food, water, and cosmetics. Additionally, difficulties in reading labels were mentioned as barriers to obtaining information. The lack of transparency from the industry and authorities, as well as the limited dissemination of the results of scientific studies on the impact of chemicals on health, are also referred to as concerns.

Participants acknowledged a shift, and substances once considered safe are now recognized as potentially harmful.

“Mas pessoas que não tenham tantos conhecimentos acabam por não estar tão atentos. Se calhar, imagina, na escolha de um iogurte vão pelo sabor, ou se calhar pela publicidade que lhes pareceu mais cativante, em vez de estarem realmente cientes da decisão que estão a tomar.”

“But people who don't have as much knowledge end up not being so attentive. Maybe, imagine, when choosing a yoghurt they go for the flavor, or maybe for the advertising that seems most appealing to them, rather than really being aware of the decision they're making.” [female 25 years old]

“Aliás, as letras, quando são muito pequeninas, é para nós não fazermos tempo a ler, não é? Porque é sinal de que não é boa peça levarmos para nós.”

“In fact, when the letters are very small, it's so that we don't take the time to read them, isn't it? Because it's a sign that it's not a good item to take with you.” [female 56 years old]

“(…) e mesmo quando estão a queimar a palha do arroz, que temos aqui dias infinitos com um cheiro terrível, pronto, também nunca sabemos muito bem o que é que isso nos anda a fazer, não é?”

“(…) and even when they're burning the rice straw, which we have endless days here with a terrible smell, well, we never really know what it's doing to us either, do we?” [female, 50 years old]

Secondly, a widespread apprehension about the health impact of chemical exposure was addressed, with an emphasis on the consequences of regular and long-term exposure to various hazards that are not easily perceived, such as in the case of radiation exposure.

“No caso da tomografia computadorizada. (...) e estamos a substituí-la [a ecografia] por tomografia computadorizada. E a longo prazo vamos pagar isto do excessivo das radiações, porque não se vê, não se sente, não é? Mas está lá, é cumulativo.”

“In the case of computed tomography (...) and we're replacing it [ultrasound] with computed tomography. And in the long term we're going to pay for this excessive radiation, because you can't see it, you can't feel it, can you? But it's there, it's cumulative.” [female, 46 years old]

Another topic of concern was related to the fact that cultural and generational habits, rooted in the use of chemical products, especially among the elderly population, make it difficult to adopt healthier, safer, and more sustainable alternatives. On top of that, resistance to change, motivated by inertia, lack of accessible alternatives, or the influence of social groups, can constitute obstacles to behavior change.

“É a rutura de hábitos. Ou seja, estou inserida num contexto, numa cultura, não é? Toda a gente faz aquilo à minha volta. Porque é que eu não hei-de fazer também? Ou seja, no meu grupo de amigos é tudo, comem de tudo. Eu, sendo vegetariana no meio do meu grupo de amigos, vou ser como se fosse um empecilho, porque quando vamos jantar fora tem que haver alternativa para mim. Há um monte de hábitos que eu tenho que eles não têm. Por isso, às vezes, também a resistência à mudança e a vontade de romper com os hábitos, comparado com a sociedade em que nos rodeia.”

“It's breaking habits. In other words, I'm part of a context, a culture, right? Everyone does it around me. Why shouldn't I do it too? In other words, my group of friends eat everything. Me being a vegetarian in the middle of my group of friends is going to be like a hindrance, because when we go out for dinner there has to be an alternative for me. There are a lot of habits I have that they don't have. That's why sometimes there's also resistance to change and a desire to break with habits, compared to the society around us.” [female, 28 years old]

“É a cultura deles. Cresceram neste ambiente, habituaram-se a pensar assim e não vale a pena.”

“It's their culture. They've grown up in this environment, they've got used to thinking like this and it's not worth it.” [male, 57 years old]

“E mesmo relativamente à alimentação, essa população também tem outros hábitos e que provavelmente há muitas pessoas de mais idade no nosso mercado, mas nunca leram um rótulo. Exato. Pegam não aquele alimento que é habitual, comprarem aquilo e vão continuar a comprar aquilo.”

“And even when it comes to food, this population also has other habits and there are probably many older people in our market who have never read a label. That's right. They don't buy the food they're used to, they buy it and they're going to keep buying it.” [female, 50 years old]

Fourth, several economic and social factors were pointed out as barriers to limiting the use of chemicals. Population growth was seen as a primary factor behind the excessive reliance on chemicals, namely in food production. Moreover, participants verbalized that the higher cost of organic products and other healthier alternatives often limit access to this type of food.

“Eu penso que tudo isto gira à volta do aumento da população no nosso planeta. Porque nós vivemos, as pessoas, a população aumenta, isso implica mais produção, a população tem que comer. Ora, (...) para haver produção, (...) se não se põe um químico, a lagarta come a couve, fura a maçã, e nós dizemos assim,

a maçã furada é a melhor. Muito bem, só que a gente vai ao supermercado vender e dizem assim, esta maçã não presta, está deita fora porque não tem os parâmetros que a União Europeia, obriga.”

“I think all this revolves around the increase in population on our planet. Because we live, people, the population increases, that means more production, the population has to eat. Now, (...) for there to be production, (...) if you don't put a chemical on it, the caterpillar eats the cabbage, bores into the apple, and we say, the bored apple is the best. Very well, but we go to the supermarket to sell it, and they say, this apple is no good, throw it away because it doesn't meet the standards that the European Union requires.” [male, 60 years old]

The normalization of chemical use in today's society was also pinpointed as a potential problem, often justified by the need for food production and pest control, which often contributes to a lack of apprehension about their impacts.

“(...) vão um bocadinho no sentido de aquilo que eu estava a dizer, tudo é químico, um tomate normal também é químico. Generalizam aquilo que eu estava a dizer, quer tudo mau ou tanto faz, não é?”

“(...) they go a bit in the direction of what I was saying, everything is chemical, a normal tomato is also chemical. They generalize what I was saying whether it's all bad or whatever, don't they?” [male, 57 years old]

Concerns about workplace chemical exposure were also prominent, with examples including inadequate air filtration systems and insufficient safety measures for handling hazardous substances. Participants highlighted the lack of action from occupational health authorities as a persistent issue.

“Preocupa-me imensa qualidade do ar que respiramos, não só o ar ambiental mas também o ar dentro das instituições onde trabalhamos. Os ares condicionados a que estamos sujeitos. Posso falar da minha experiência que trabalho muitas das vezes 16 horas dentro do meu serviço e que saio lá com irritações na vista, irritações na garganta, garganta seca e pronto. E parece que depois falamos com a segurança no trabalho, falamos com a saúde ocupacional, peço desculpa às pessoas aqui presentes, mas que é uma luta inglória porque continuamos com mais do mesmo.”

“I'm very concerned about the quality of the air we breathe, not only the environmental air but also the air inside the institutions where we work. The air conditioning we're subjected to. I can tell you from my experience that I often work 16 hours in my office, and I leave with irritated eyes, irritated throat, dry throat and that's it. And it seems that afterwards we talk to occupational safety, we talk to occupational health, I apologise to the people here, but it's an inglorious struggle because we're still stuck with more of the same.” [female, 46 years old]

Finally, a concern about the need for more (effective) regulation and political action was expressed. Indeed, there was a strong belief that stricter government regulation is essential to control the use of chemicals and protect public health. The lack of action on the part of the authorities, the ineffectiveness of existing control mechanisms and mistrust in the industry were cited as frustrating.

“É um bocado difícil. Ou há uma solução política para isso, vai-se deixar tudo andar assim. Começa-se a ver a população a ficar doente e a desaparecer, e continuam a pensar que a solução é esta. Mas também ainda ninguém falou, por exemplo, em termos de saúde pública.”

“It’s a bit difficult. Either there’s a political solution to this, or we’re going to let everything go on like this. You start to see the population getting sick and disappearing, and they keep thinking that this is the solution. But nobody has talked about public health either.” [male, 60 years old]

Information and literacy

A variety of perspectives and challenges related to information and literacy concerning chemicals and environmental health were identified, reflecting an emphasis on the need for more health and environmental literacy.

The importance of promoting health and environmental literacy was recognized. Furthermore, participants acknowledged the need to educate future generations, particularly young people, transmitting knowledge and values that promote healthier and more sustainable choices.

“Até mesmo se estivessem a ter uma conversa, até mesmo com crianças, basta elas começarem a perceber que se calhar já começam a trazer determinados hábitos para as casas. (...) Que se começarem a falar também sobre estes assuntos, rapidamente começa a ser um tópico que eles começam a ouvir e se calhar mais tarde na sua vida adulta começam a interiorizar e as escolas se calhar também começam a abordar muito mais a temática porque veem que a criança está interessada.”

“Even if they were having a conversation, even with children, all they must do is start to realize that maybe they’re already bringing certain habits into their homes. (...) That if they also start talking about these issues, it quickly becomes a topic that they start to hear about and maybe later in their adult lives they start to internalize it, and maybe schools also start to approach the subject a lot more because they see that the child is interested.” [female, 25 years old]

Although participants mentioned the difficulty in accessing reliable information on chemicals and their impacts, several sources are regularly used. The internet was identified as the main source of information. However, they also expressed the need to validate information obtained online in other sources and vice-versa, having caution in looking for reliable websites.

Apart from the internet, other sources of information were mentioned, namely television programs and documentaries (especially educational programs and documentaries), scientific journals and books, personal networks (friends, health professions, and experts in areas such as chemistry and health), and food labels.

To note, though, that participants complained that information rarely is “offered” to them. When they need to know something, they have to search for it.

“Eu por acaso no nono ano tive uma disciplina de saúde. Apesar de na altura não ser a área que eu queria escolher. Isto é importante e realmente há alguns conselhos que recebi durante esse ano que foram úteis e ainda continuo a manter. O resto da informação é obtido através de... no fundo, através das notícias.”

“I happened to have a health subject in ninth grade. Although at the time it wasn’t the area I wanted to choose. This is important and there is some advice I received during that year that was useful and I still keep it. The rest of the information I get from... the news, basically.” [male, 46 years old]

“Geralmente procuro, raramente vem ter connosco.”

“I usually look for it, it rarely comes to us.” [female, 56 years old]

“E, portanto, eu quando tenho alguma dúvida, tenho alguns amigos que são químicos. (...) Então sempre que eu tenho alguma dúvida de algo, eu contacto a eles. Ou então, realmente, na internet, não é? Quando se ouve falar de qualquer coisa nas notícias.”

“And so when I have any doubts, I have some friends who are chemists. (...) So whenever I have any doubts about something, I contact them. Or really, on the internet, isn't it? When you hear about something on the news.” [female, 48 years old]

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) to obtain information about products and their components was briefly mentioned as a possibility, although with concerns about its reliability.

“Não, vou-me informando. Aliás, hoje em dia temos o recurso. Não é totalmente, pronto, é fiável, mas não é a 100%, digamos assim. Por inteligência artificial, podemos fazer uma nomenclatura. Vou ao supermercado, diz-me de acordo com a informação que tu tens da indústria, respetiva, o que é que o produto comporta. E ele vai-me dizer, e em percentagem.”

“No, I'll find out. In fact, nowadays we have a resource. It's not totally reliable, but it's not 100 per cent, so to speak. Artificial intelligence can be categorized. I go to the supermarket, it tells me, according to the information you have from the industry, what the product contains. And it will tell me, and in percentages.” [male, 60 years old]

Besides the already mentioned need for more information about chemicals and their effects on health, participants also discussed the necessity for clear, concise, and accessible information, available for the general public, avoiding complex technical language that makes understanding difficult.

“Sim, no fundo educar as pessoas para (...) para ler o rótulo pelo menos de vez em quando.”

“Yes, basically educating people to (...) read the label at least once in a while.” [male, 46 years old]

“Eu, uma coisa que me preocupa bastante é o mercúrio no peixe. E eu acho que até há bastantes estudos, mas eu não vejo a população geral a falar disso. Porque eu acho que essa informação não está disseminada para o público. Se eu for perguntar aos meus pais o que é que tu achas destes níveis que podem ser perigosos, eles não vão saber do que é que eu estou a falar. E eu acho que isso é bastante importante. E utilizar os momentos em que, por exemplo, o horário nobre, o telejornal, onde está toda a gente a jantar e a ver. E usar esse tempo precioso, em vez de ser mais notícias e notícias de coisas que não têm interesse nenhum, usar esse tempo para educar a população. Acho muito importante isso. E eu acho que Portugal está a falhar muito nesse aspeto. Não há, não há a propagação da informação para toda a gente. Eu e a (...) estamos a estudar nutrição, se calhar até sabemos mais disto. Mas a minha avó não sabe e vai continuar a fazer a vida dela como aprendeu há 50 anos. E as coisas estão mudadas. As preocupações são diferentes agora.”

“One thing that worries me a lot is mercury in fish. And I think there are quite a few studies, but I don't see the general population talking about it. Because I don't think this information is disseminated to the

public. If I ask my parents what you think about these levels that could be dangerous, they won't know what I'm talking about. And I think that's very important. And to use the moments when, for example, prime time, the news, when everyone is having dinner and watching. And to use that precious time, instead of being more news and news about things that are of no interest, to use that time to educate the population. I think that's very important. And I think Portugal is failing a lot in this respect. There isn't, there isn't the spread of information to everyone. (...) and I am studying nutrition, so maybe we know more about it. But my grandmother doesn't and she's going to carry on with her life as she learnt 50 years ago. And things have changed. The concerns are different now” [female, 20 years old]

Difficulties in accessing reliable information were also expressed, associated with a generalized distrust of information from industry and the media, considering that economic interests can influence the dissemination of information. Additionally, a proliferation of contradictory information online was considered to hinder the identification of reliable sources and form solid opinions. The lack of time and motivation to research information in depth was also pointed out as an obstacle to health and environmental literacy.

“E há aqui um problema de motivação, estar motivada para se informar. Porque a informação muda, e é muito complexa. E há coisas que fazem mal a uma pessoa e não fazem à própria pessoa que está a procurar a informação. É preciso a pessoa estar motivada para isso, e isso é complicado.”

“And there's a problem of motivation here, of being motivated to get informed. Because information changes, and it's very complex. And there are things that hurt a person and don't hurt the person looking for the information. You have to be motivated to do it, and that's complicated.” [male, 57 years old]

“E como há um bocado estavam a dizer se a informação fosse dada de um modo mais claro e fosse acessível, se calhar as pessoas aí já começavam a olhar para tudo se calhar não é uma informação que está a ser impingida. Eu tenho à minha frente uma outra informação para a qual eu posso olhar e posso optar acreditar ou mudar determinado estilo de vida por causa disso. Mas eu acho que por vezes nós simplesmente não queremos mudar, porque não queremos olhar para o que está à nossa frente.”

“And as you were saying a moment ago, if the information was given in a clearer and more accessible way, maybe people would start to look at it all - maybe it's not information that's being pushed on them. I have other information in front of me that I can look at and I can choose to believe or change my lifestyle because of it. But I think that sometimes we simply don't want to change, because we don't want to look at what's in front of us.” [female, 25 years old]

In terms of strategies to overcome difficulties, several were listed. For example, the creation of online platforms with reliable information from trusted sources or the diversification of the means of communication, such as television programs, newspaper reports and awareness-raising campaigns, as a way of reaching different audiences. Other strategies include the use of simplified language and the adaptation of information to different audiences, as well as integrating education for health and environmental literacy into school curricula from an early age.

“(…) tópico interessante, que é mesmo no apoio que as escolas podem dar nessa formação. Eu já não falo escolas a nível de formação avançada, universidades. Se desde as creches, desde quando eles são mesmo crianças começarem a transmitir determinados valores, acho que muito mais depressa a pessoa acaba por crescer com essa ideia.”

“(…) an interesting topic, which is the support that schools can give in this training. I'm not talking about schools or universities. If from nursery school onwards, from when they're really children, they start to pass on certain values, I think the person will grow up with this idea much more quickly.” [female, 29 years old]

“Mas acima de tudo apostar na simplicidade da informação que é transmitida porque as pessoas ouvem falar em nomes extremamente complicados perdem o interesse não é para mim.”

“But above all to focus on the simplicity of the information that is transmitted because when people hear extremely complicated names, they lose interest.” [female, 28 years old]

Within this topic, areas of future research were another discussed theme. The emerging ideas entailed studying the effects of chemicals on biodiversity and water quality, as well as effective communication strategies to promote health and environmental literacy, taking into account the different audiences and their needs.

Health consequences of exposure

Although some participants only talked about general effects associated with exposure to chemicals, the majority could verbalize several health problems, cancer being the most frequently mentioned. Other health problems included endocrine diseases, respiratory diseases, autoimmune diseases, kidney diseases, neurodegenerative diseases and malformations, cognitive/mental health effects, fertility problems, allergies, eye problems, gastric effects, and skin problems.

“Para mim é tudo o que tem a ver com os problemas respiratórios. Podem até mesmo ser alergias, sejam elas cutâneas ou aquelas de, por exemplo, asma também. É um problema respiratório, não deixa de o ser. Há pessoas que, com determinados químicos, por exemplo, a utilizar poderão até mesmo ficar cegos. Eu acho que os problemas há de vários tipos. Por exemplo, estética, unhas. Há pessoas que podem desenvolver problemas, não digo micoses, cancro nas unhas. Há pessoas que, por usarem produtos no cabelo, ou até mesmo em zonas mais íntimas, poderão estar a desenvolver outro tipo de infeções que estão agora a ser cada vez mais faladas, com as questões da beleza e tudo mais.”

“For me, it's everything to do with respiratory problems. They can even be allergies, whether skin allergies or, for example, asthma. It's a respiratory problem all the same. There are people who may even go blind from using certain chemicals, for example. I think there are all kinds of problems. For example, aesthetics, nails. There are people who can develop problems, I don't mean mycoses, nail cancer. There are people who, by using products on their hair, or even in more intimate areas, could be developing other types of infections that are now being talked about more and more, with beauty issues and everything else.” [female, 25 years old]

Regulation

The analysis of citizens' perspectives on the regulation of the use of chemicals reveals a growing awareness of the risks associated with exposure to these substances and a sense for more robust political action to protect public health and the environment. Within this dimension, several topics were discussed. First, the existence of a lack of regulation and disregard for existing regulations. Participants also expressed that authorities do not communicate in a transparent way control results for foodstuffs, water and other products. The imposition of sanctions by the European Union on Portugal for non-compliance with standards related to the presence of chemicals in products is seen as an indicator of the ineffectiveness of national control mechanisms.

“E isto pôs-me a pensar claramente que há coisas que são legais e que são comercializadas com uma facilidade que é estranhíssima, eu não acreditava. Ela trabalha em venenos há 25 anos e ela diz como é que é possível que o glifosato possa ser comercializado da forma que é. E então acho que isso mostra que realmente não há qualquer tipo de controlo. Eu sei que há, até na Europa mais do que outros países, nem se quer vou falar dos Estados Unidos. Mas dentro da Europa eu acho que é gravíssimo certas coisas serem legais.”

“And this clearly made me think that there are things that are legal and that are commercialised with an ease that is very strange, I didn't believe it. She's been working in poisons for 25 years and she says how is it possible that glyphosate can be commercialised in the way that it is? And so I think that shows that there really isn't any kind of control. I know there is, even in Europe more than in other countries, I'm not even going to mention the United States. But within Europe I think it's extremely serious that certain things are legal.” [female, 31 years old]

“(…) parece não haver regulamentação ou se houver, não é respeitada o suficiente no que diz respeito à distribuição do químico no ar.”

“(…) there seems to be no regulation, or if there is, it's not respected enough with regard to the distribution of the chemical in the air.” [female, 28 years old]

In this context, the importance of holding industries accountable for their environmental impact, particularly regarding chemical emissions and hazardous waste management was highlighted.

Participants also verbalized how some laws seem to favor the use of certain chemicals. One topic already discussed above, the population growth and the need for large-scale food production put some pressure and often are used to justify the intensive use of chemicals in agriculture. Some participants expressed frustration that critical regulations, particularly those banning harmful chemicals, often take years to implement.

Similarly, some European Union standards, by establishing aesthetic quality standards for agricultural products, sometimes encourage the use of chemicals, to guarantee the uniformity and ‘perfect’ appearance of products. And compulsory land clearing was pointed out as a factor that drives the use of herbicides, to the detriment of more sustainable methods.

“Eu penso que tudo isto gira à volta do aumento da população no nosso planeta. Porque nós vivemos, as pessoas, a população aumenta, isso implica mais produção, a população tem que comer. Ora, coisa em dia, para haver produção, se não houver químicos (…).”

“I think all this revolves around the increase in population on our planet. Because we live, people, the population increases, that means more production, the population must eat. Nowadays, for there to be production, if there are no chemicals (…).” [male, 60 years old]

“As grandes manifestações dos agricultores foi por causa disso, não conseguem concorrer com outros países, porque utilizam produtos químicos aos quais eles estão proibidos de utilizar.”

“The big demonstrations by farmers were because of this, they can't compete with other countries because they use chemicals that they are forbidden to use.” [male, 60 years old]

“Há outro aspeto que eu gostaria de falar. Os herbicidas sempre, pronto, ultimamente. Ou melhor, utilizavam-se e penso que se continuam a utilizar. E penso que ultimamente com mais frequência. Até porque hoje em dia com a história da obrigatoriedade de limpeza dos terrenos, eu vejo que em algumas zonas passou-se a utilizar mais os herbicidas.”

“There's another aspect I'd like to talk about. Herbicides have always been used recently. Or rather, they were used, and I think they are still being used. And I think they've been used more often recently. Not least because nowadays, with the obligatory land clearing, I can see that herbicides have been used more in some areas.” [male, 63 years old]

The need for stronger political action was advocated by strengthening consumer defense mechanisms, with greater transparency in disseminating information about the presence of chemicals in products and in monitoring compliance with regulations. Moreover, the need to invest in research and development into alternatives to chemicals, particularly in agriculture, is pointed out as crucial to guaranteeing the production of healthy food and the protection of the environment. And banning the use of chemicals proven to be harmful to human health and the environment was defended by some participants.

“E, portanto, às vezes também escasseia dinheiro para pagar as pesquisas, deteção e quantificação de químicos nos alimentos, na água de consumo humano não tenho tanta certeza. (...) A partir de 2010 ele disse, mas continuamos a pagar uma fatura pesadíssima pelo que aconteceu na agricultura quando ainda não era proibida a utilização desses produtos. Também adubos de síntese, nitratos de síntese também, continuamos a pagar uma fatura pesadíssima em termos de doença. Humanos e também noutros animais, mas em humanos, de modo que há realmente aqui um vastíssimo campo a investigar e a exigir que as entidades oficiais nos permitam aceder, porque por vezes creio que a defesa do consumidor em Portugal não é quase, mas quase parece embrionária e nós precisávamos saber muito mais do que aquilo que sabemos, nomeadamente nestas matérias.”

“And so sometimes money is also scarce to pay for research, detection and quantification of chemicals in food, in drinking water I'm not so sure. (...) From 2010 onwards, he said, but we are still paying a very heavy bill for what happened in agriculture when the use of these products was not yet banned. Synthetic fertilisers, synthetic nitrates too, we're still paying a very heavy bill in terms of disease. In humans and also in other animals, but in humans, so there really is a vast field here to investigate and to demand that the official entities allow us access, because sometimes I believe that consumer protection in Portugal is not almost, but almost seems embryonic and we needed to know much more than what we know, particularly in these matters.” [female, 67 years old]

“Às vezes nós, população, conseguimos muita coisa, mas também não demonstramos o peso da nossa união.”

“Sometimes we, the people, achieve a lot, but we don't demonstrate the weight of our unity either.” [female, 67 years old]

Lastly, participants have shown themselves to be aware of the importance of changing consumption habits, opting for organic products and encouraging local and sustainable production. However, there was acknowledged that products free of harmful chemicals are difficult to find (and sometimes they seem to be produced in less quantity) and often expensive, and that the burden of choosing safer alternatives falls disproportionately on consumers, especially those with lower incomes.

“Eu ia dizer que pode ir aos locais da região, ter os mercados que é o agricultor próprio é que os vende. E depois também há vários sítios em que (...) são associações de vários agricultores em que a fruta que tem mais dimensões ou menos (...). Em que eles entregam a baixo preço(...) só que é sazonal a fruta que há da época e que seja desperdício. E acho que é por aí que também temos que usar a fruta.”

“I was going to say that you can go to places in the region, there are markets where the farmer sells it himself. And then there are also various places where (...) there are associations of various farmers where the fruit is bigger or smaller (...). They deliver it at a low price (...) but the fruit that's in season and that's waste is seasonal. And I think that's why we also have to use the fruit.” [female, 56 years old]

“Aliás, eu queria só...É mais em jeito de pergunta, quem possa responder, pode ser que eu esteja errado nesse aspeto, é assim, já se falou aqui muito da agricultura biológica. Tentar intercalar entre os produtos industrializados com a agricultura biológica, mas, por exemplo, eu pelo menos, se calhar erradamente, considero que há duas barreiras logo para o consumidor. Em primeiro lugar é o preço dos produtos biológicos geralmente são mais elevados, e o produto biológico não é atrativo em termos de aspeto para o consumidor. Não sei se...”

“In fact, I just wanted to... I'm more of a questioner, whoever can answer, maybe I'm wrong on this point, it's like this, there's been a lot of talk about organic farming. Trying to intersperse industrialized products with organic farming, but, for example, I at least, perhaps wrongly, think that there are two barriers for the consumer. Firstly, the price of organic products is generally higher, and organic products are not attractive in terms of appearance for the consumer. I don't know if...” [male, 46 years old]

Individual protection strategies

When asked about which protection strategies they used in their daily lives against the exposure to chemicals, several were nominated. One included, as mentioned above, the pro-active search for multiples sources of information to triangulate the acquired knowledge and assure its trustworthiness. Interestingly, AI emerged as a useful tool to search for information and decision making, although it was recognized that this is not a 100% reliable source. Another adopted strategy was a critical reading of food labels to identify ingredients to be avoided and explore healthier alternatives. Additionally, the adoption of hygienization/sanitizing practices of food, especially with natural products, was another pointed out behavior. The use of activated carbon filters to purify water was another strategy mentioned, despite the recognition of its ineffectiveness in removing all chemical contaminants. Behavior change was widely referred at different levels, from choosing food from organic farming or growing one's own food at home, in gardens or small backyards, to a reduction in the consumption of processed and fried foods, the use of natural cleaning products and personal care products with natural ingredients, as well as the use of adequate protection clothing/equipment. Faced with the recognized impossibility of completely avoiding exposure to chemicals, some interviewees stated that they opt to adopt an attitude of ‘disconnection’ or a switch the chip off mindset to avoid worry about the exposure.

“Eu, pelo menos, eu nunca leio só uma página. Eu, por exemplo, quando é sobre os produtos, eu tento ir mesmo à página do produto. Ok. E quando é sobre coisas no geral, eu tento ver três ou quatro páginas e normalmente, quando três ou quatro dizem mais ou menos a mesma coisa, é porque a informação é verdadeira. É assim que eu me tento guiar.”

"I, at least, never read just one page. For example, when it's about products, I try to go to the actual product page. Okay. And when it's about things in general, I try to look at three or four pages and usually, when three or four say more or less the same thing, it's because the information is true. That's how I try to guide myself." [female, 29 years old]

"Sim, em termos de alimentos, o que eu tento minimizar é higienizá-los muito bem e tentar neutralizar os químicos, porque há formas de o fazermos em casa. Com produtos mais naturais (...)."

"Yes, in terms of food, what I try to minimize is to sanitize it very well and try to neutralize the chemicals, because there are ways of doing this at home. With more natural products (...)." [female, 56 years old]

"Não comer. Por exemplo, eu não como nada que seja fritos e minimizo sempre que tenho que almoçar fora, principalmente de almoçar fora."

"I don't eat. For example, I don't eat anything that's fried and I minimize it whenever I have to go out for lunch, especially lunch out." [female, 56 years old]

"Tudo o que é mais processado, eu evito."

"Anything more processed, I avoid." [female, 31 years old]

"Acho que vou só então mencionar aqui um pormenor. Eu acho que por vezes o homem tem a capacidade de se distanciar da realidade, por vezes quando começa a ouvir determinadas coisas assume que só acontece na América ou só acontece nas Áfricas e nas Ásias de vida."

"I think I'll just mention one detail here. I think that sometimes people have the ability to distance themselves from reality, sometimes when they hear certain things they assume that it only happens in America or only happens in the Africas and Asias of life." [female, 25 years old]

Contexts of (increased) risk

Participants' speeches highlighted various contexts where exposure to hazardous chemicals is likely to be increased. Living conditions close to industrial or agricultural sites with intense activity were pointed out as a relevant risk factor. In line with this idea, practicing physical exercise in these areas can be also problematic.

"E aqui na zona onde vivo, aqui ninguém pensa nisso, acho que essas coisas são mais citadinas, mais urbanas. As pessoas (...) Estão sempre a pulverizar, eu faço exercício, às vezes vou a correr, estão os tratores a passar a pulverizar. E por acaso já me aconteceu, ir a passar e durante alguns momentos não conseguir abrir os olhos, porque tive contacto com os sulfatos e com os produtos que eles usam na pulverização."

"And here, where I live, nobody thinks about it, I think these things are more urban. People (...) They're always spraying, I'm exercising, sometimes I go for a run, tractors are passing by spraying. And it's happened to me, going past and for a few moments not being able to open my eyes, because I've come into contact with the sulphates and the products they use in spraying." [male, 57 years old]

Water and soil contamination was a recurring shared concern. In this sense, community gardens that use (ground)water potentially contaminated by former industrial activities to irrigate their soils were another example of increased risk.

“Também venho de um contexto um pouco mais rural, no sítio em que há culturas intensivas, até que ponto é que os químicos não vão contaminar os lençóis freáticos e tudo mais. Isso também é um pouco preocupante, porque ao fim ao cabo, não há nenhuma maneira de estarmos livres de alguma coisa, até mesmo a água canalizada utiliza-se químicos e tudo mais para estar em condições de nós a bebermos.”

“I also come from a slightly more rural background, where there's intensive cultivation, to what extent the chemicals aren't going to contaminate the groundwater and everything else. That's also a bit worrying, because at the end of the day, there's no way we're going to be free of anything, even piped water uses chemicals and everything else to make it fit for us to drink.” [female, 28 years old]

The school environment was also conveyed as a source of concern, with the quality of food served in canteens being questioned and the existence of dangerous materials in some schools, such as zinc roof tiles and asbestos. Similarly, the work environment has relevant challenges that should be thought of as workers can be exposed to dangerous chemicals in factories, laboratories and hospitals. On top of that, the lack of adequate protection measures, such as the absence of efficient ventilation systems and the fact that the air conditioning filters are not regularly cleaned, may aggravate the situation.

“Quero também só mencionar que muitas vezes o ambiente onde estamos inseridos também influencia bastante o tipo de exposição que temos. Por exemplo, alguém que esteja nas escolas, a nível da alimentação, a comida que nos colocam à frente é a comida que nós comemos. Não interessa a marca do iogurte, a quantidade de químicos que está lá, o tipo de alimento que nos colocam no prato. Muitas vezes nem sequer temos de onde é que veio o frango, por exemplo. Quanto tipo de químicos é que o pobrezinho foi injetado antes de vir para o prato. Se as verduras eram biológicas ou não. E isto não se aplica só a alguém que está numa cama de hospital. Para além de estar rodeado com aqueles químicos, mais uma vez, tudo o que está à sua volta está tão controlado que a exposição acaba por estar longe do controlo da própria pessoa. Porque a pessoa, ao invés de estar a poder ter a opção de optar sequer ou não de determinada coisa, é aquilo que está à sua frente.”

“I also just want to mention that often the environment we're in also has a big influence on the kind of exposure we get. For example, if you're in school, when it comes to food, the food they put in front of you is the food you eat. It doesn't matter what brand the yoghurt is, how many chemicals are in it, what kind of food they put on your plate. Often, we don't even know where the chicken came from, for example. What kind of chemicals the poor thing was injected with before it came to the plate. Whether the vegetables were organic or not. And this doesn't just apply to someone in a hospital bed. Apart from being surrounded by those chemicals, once again, everything around them is so controlled that the exposure ends up being far from the person's own control. Because instead of having the option of choosing whether or not to eat something, it's what's in front of them.” [female, 25 years old]

“Eu partilho da opinião de todas as pessoas aqui presentes nesta reunião. Preocupa-me imensa qualidade do ar que respiramos, não só o ar ambiental mas também o ar dentro das instituições onde trabalhamos. Os ares condicionados a que estamos sujeitos. Posso falar da minha experiência que trabalho muitas das

vezes 16 horas dentro do meu serviço e que saio lá com irritações na vista, irritações na garganta, garganta seca e pronto.”

“I share the opinion of everyone here at this meeting. I'm very concerned about the quality of the air we breathe, not only the environmental air but also the air inside the institutions where we work. The air conditioning we are subjected to. I can tell you from my own experience that I often work 16 hours in my office and I come out with irritated eyes, irritated throat, dry throat and that's it.” [female, 46 years old]

Vulnerable groups

Although not being one of the most discussed topics, several populations were identified as more vulnerable: children, elderly, pregnant women, people with pre-existing health conditions, those who practice sports, people with lower literacy levels and lower income households.

Pathways of exposure

The participants showed some knowledge regarding possible pathways of exposure to hazardous chemicals across different daily life contexts. Inhalation of airborne chemicals was one primarily mentioned with specific risks being associated with proximity to industrial sites, and traffic and agricultural areas. Air particles and residues were discussed to have a harmful effect due to their contamination of air, water, and soil. Air quality indoors was another concern, being associated with several respiratory diseases.

Ingestion was another significant route identified, with contamination of drinking water, food and agricultural products (including community gardens) posing considerable risks. Instances of glyphosate detected in non-professional populations further underscored widespread, unnoticed exposure pathways.

Skin contact was acknowledged as another significant route of exposure, particularly through cosmetics or contaminated food, and also at the workplace, through handling chemicals, being then emphasized the need for adequate protective measures.

Interviewees also mentioned that exposure can be amplified through rainwater runoff, industrial emissions, and inadequate waste management. The chain does not stop here and the way human exposure can indirectly impact ecosystems and biodiversity, creating a feedback loop of harm to health and the environment, was also discussed.

“Ainda dentro desse tópico, acho que também é interessante mencionar que muitas das vezes há também a experiência, através das chuvas, desse género de químicos pela água. As pessoas também não estão conscientes desse género de questões, porque depois vão passar férias a uma praia fluvial ou até mesmo a água do mar e começam a ficar com a pele irritada e nunca percebem bem o porquê. E eu estou a dizer isto da água, mas, por exemplo, o que leva da terra também pode ir para a areia, onde nós vamos ficar. Pode ficar noutros géneros de locais em que estamos em contato e muitas vezes nem nos apercebemos que estão lá químicos que nos fazem mal, e que na volta não vieram daquele local, vieram de outros e foram arrastados para esses géneros locais.”

“Still on that topic, I think it's also worth mentioning that we often experience these kinds of chemicals in the water through the rain. People aren't aware of these kinds of issues either, because then they go on holiday to a river beach or even to sea water and their skin starts to get irritated and they never really understand why. And I'm talking about the water, but, for example, what you take from the land can also get onto the sand, where we'll be staying. It can remain in other kinds of places we come into contact with and we often don't even realize that there are chemicals there that are bad for us, and that they didn't come from that place, they came from other places and were dragged into those places.” [female 25 years old]

“Acho que o impacto, a todos os níveis. Não é só na saúde humana, nos animais, na natureza. Os químicos acho que estão em todo o lado, fala-se muito no plástico nos oceanos, mas é também na mesma medida em todo o lado.”

“I think there's an impact at all levels. It's not just on human health, on animals, on nature. I think the chemicals are everywhere, there's a lot of talk about plastic in the oceans, but it's also everywhere to the same extent.” [female 50 years old]

“Pensemos que temos um mundo inteiro, uma biodiversidade da qual nós dependemos e que nunca é conversada sequer neste tipo de coisas e, portanto, uma alienação total com o mundo em que vivemos e que, para além de nos beneficiarmos a nós, destruímos tudo à nossa volta.”

“Let's think that we have a whole world, a biodiversity on which we depend, and which is never even talked about in this kind of way and, therefore, a total alienation from the world in which we live and which, as well as benefiting us, destroys everything around us.” [female, 31 years old]

Chemicals

Finally, although in some interventions participants were not able to name the chemical that they were referring to, several ones were identified, as heavy metals (cadmium, lead, mercury, and zinc), agricultural chemicals (herbicides in general and glyphosate in particular, pesticides, and nitrates), acrylamide, asbestos and toluene, radium, sulphates, and microplastics.

3.4 Sweden

In Sweden, a total of 12 people (5 in the first focus group; 7 in the second focus group) participated in the two focus groups. The sociodemographic characterization of the participants is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Characterization of the participants (N=12).

Sociodemographic characteristics	N
Gender	
Male	6
Female	6
Age	
<35 years	6
35-54 years	3
55+ years	3
Educational level	
Non-higher degree	5
Higher degree	7
Having children	
Yes	2
No	10
Place of living	
Rural	1
Urban	11

The main themes emerging from the discussions were: 1. Sources of exposure, 2. Perspectives on the use of chemicals, 3. Information and literacy, 4. Health consequences of exposure, 5. Regulation, 6. Individual protection strategies, 7. Contexts of (increased) risk, 8. Vulnerable groups, 9. Pathways of exposure and 10. Chemicals. Each topic will be developed below, with the presentation of verbatims in Swedish, followed by the English translation.

Sources of exposure to chemicals

The following sources of exposure were identified in the focus groups: personal care products, household cleaning products, and food (for example, additives like E-numbers, being questioned their long-term effects as they accumulate in the body). Chemical pollution in oceans and ecosystems, with impacts seen in marine life and the food chain was also acknowledged. Other sources included drinking water, smoke, medical drugs, and contaminated water and soil.

“Sen finns det i kemikalier i alla hudvårdsprodukter eller väldigt många i alla fall det vet jag det är i tandkräm i alla fall och schampo och kräm. Det finns ju hur mycket som helst.”

“Then there are chemicals in all skin care products, or very many in any case, I know it is in toothpaste in any case and in shampoo and skin cream. There is so much.” [male, 55 years old]

“...Och jag vet inte hur stor koll man har på de saker som man medvetet stoppar in i mat heller. Alltså, det oroar mig. Alla E-ämnen och så, vad som händer när de anrikas i, i mig.”

“...And I don't know how much you know about the things you deliberately put into food either. So, that worries me. All the E substances and such, what happens when they are enriched in, in me.” [female, 58 years old]

“Men jag tror också det är vanligare att vi utsätts för kemikalier i kroppen från den mat vi äter, om det är vegetariskt eller kött, för man sprutar antingen, ja på grönsaker, kemikalier, eller så håller man på med sprutor och saker till djuren.”

“But I also think it’s more common for us to be exposed to chemicals in our bodies from the food we eat, whether it’s vegetarian or meat, because they either spray chemicals on vegetables or use syringes and things for animals.” [female, 19 years old]

Consumer products were also referred, namely regarding household items and consumer goods, with concerns over chemicals in personal care products, old furniture, clothes and toys, as well as potential unknown risks in commonly used items (e.g., mattresses). One participant presented concerns over imported products and their unknown chemical content and gave an example of a strong odor of gasoline from shoes bought online. Another participant reflected on potential hazards in clothing and other household items that use chemicals for coloration and production. There was a discussion on the import of goods from regions with potentially lower safety standards, leading to uncertainty over product safety despite “eco” or “safe” labeling. Clothing and food were mentioned as main sources of exposure, with the constant presence of chemicals in all areas of life being emphasized. Finally, occupational hazards like dust and exposure to plastics in warehouses were also addressed.

“Min sambo gjorde ju misstaget att han köpte ett par skor från någon utav de här sajterna. Och de kom och de luktade bensin, liksom, de där. Så de åkte ju tillbaka va. Men, det var inga bra skor alltså. (skratt) Men, det gick inte att ha dem, alltså. För att de luktade bensin. Men de var nog inte så nyttiga att ha på fötterna, heller, känner jag. Man ska nog inte lita på alla importörer heller. Som man gör.”

“My partner made the mistake of buying a pair of shoes from one of these web sites. And they came and they smelled gasoline. So they went back. But, they were no good shoes. (laughter) It was not possible to use them, because they smelled of gasoline. But they were probably not that good to wear on the feet, either, I suppose. You probably shouldn’t trust all importers either. As you do.” [female, 58 years old]

“Jag som lever som lagerarbetare, jag utsätts ju för dels mycket damm med, lager är ju inte de renaste ställena på jorden, liksom. Och vi har ju sådana här snören som är ungefär garnliknande, ett grövre. Och sen även plast då, för att alla mina pallar måste plastas, och jag måste även lägga på plast uppe på själva pallen, så att det liksom plastas in, som en låda, så att ingen kan ta nåt,”

“As someone who works as a warehouse worker, I am exposed to a lot of dust, because warehouses are not the cleanest places on earth, you know. And we have these strings that are somewhat yarn-like, a thicker kind. And then also plastic, because all my pallets have to be wrapped in plastic, and I also have to put plastic on top of the pallets, so that it is like boxed in, so that no one can take anything,” [male, 47 years old]

“Jag tänker mest på brandmän. Kanske den röken de andas in och så.”

“I mainly think about firefighters. Maybe the smoke they inhale and so on.” [male, 27 years old]

Perspectives on the use of chemicals

Two perspectives on the use of chemicals were discussed within the groups. In terms of benefits, participants highlighted how chemicals as medical drugs can have benefits for human health. Additionally, chemicals allow us

to give functions we want to have, such as colorants and fragrances. Regarding concerns and barriers, fear and anxiety were expressed, as chemicals evoke fear due to a lack of knowledge about their presence in everyday items and their impact on health. Also, an underlying uncertainty was discussed. Participants expressed doubt about what qualifies as a chemical and its potential harmful effects (e.g., in food, air, and consumer products). At different moments, participants discussed the general lack of consumer understanding regarding ingredients, e.g., the reference to "E133" and what it represents. Skepticism about information has also emerged with a concern over mixed messages, misinformation, and the struggle to determine factual information, leading to a general sense of "chemical anxiety." One recalled health alerts about food additives (or trans fats in chips) and how these discoveries often emerge only after prolonged consumer exposure, followed by skepticism about whether the alarm results in industry changes. Another concern that appeared in the discussion was desensitization and resignation. Some participants feel desensitized due to the widespread presence of chemicals, while others feel resigned to exposure ("half-defeated"). Resignation to the idea of not knowing everything about chemical exposure was expressed, as complete avoidance feels overwhelming.

"Ja, ..., ja, lite dåligt samvete för att jag lät mina barn ha plastleksaker att tugga på när de var små, till exempel. Det var säkert inget bra. Svårt att veta. Det har varit svårt att veta."

"Yes, ...yes, a little guilty for letting my kids have plastic toys to chew on when they were little, for example. It certainly wasn't good. Hard to know. It has been hard to know." [female, 58 years old]

"Ja innehållsförteckning duger ju tyvärr inte, i och med att, "Det är E133" – Jaha, men det vet jag inte vad det innebär. Men det är fortfarande ett E-ämne. Ska det vara dåligt? Kanske, kanske inte?"

"Yes, the ingredient list unfortunately isn't enough, since, "It's E133" – Oh, but I don't know what that means. But it's still an E-substance. Should it be bad? Maybe, maybe not?" [male, 34 years old]

"Jag tänker lite på objektivitet. Etthundratusen kemikalier! Så det är ganska svårt att ha en lång lista av..."

"I'm thinking a bit about objectivity. One hundred thousand chemicals! So it's quite difficult to have a long list of: "This is okay" and "This is not okay." [female, 32 years old]

"...man tappar lite av förtroende faktiskt, ja, men vad? Vi kan inte bestämma om det är farligt eller inte, särskilt med det här informationsflödet på nätet,"

"...you lose a bit of trust actually, yes, but what? We can't decide if it's dangerous or not, especially with this flow of information online." [male, 49 years old]

Additionally, the choice between organic and non-organic foods was discussed, highlighting consumer concerns over chemicals in foods like bananas and the impact of price on buying decisions. Organic eggs seen as a healthier choice, were brought up into the light, with the explanation that regulatory feed choices can inadvertently increase chemical exposure, highlighting potential policy oversights. Quite recently, Swedish TV reported that, in order to provide enough protein hens producing organic eggs are fed with fish from sustainable fishing, but this fish is rich in dioxins, PFAS etc. Conventionally produced eggs are fed with synthetic food, which is not accepted in organic farming, but contains less contamination from such pollutants.

"Det är mera kemikalier i ekologiska ägg än i vanliga ägg så att det är mer nyttigt att äta vanliga ägg än ekologiska ägg, tack vare att EU bestämde att det ska vara ett visst foder än för vanliga höns."

“There are more chemicals in organic eggs than in regular eggs, so it is more beneficial to eat regular eggs than organic eggs, thanks to the EU deciding that it should be a certain feed than for ordinary chickens.” [male, 55 years old]

Mental health and stress issues were also addressed. Stress related to the inability to control or avoid chemicals might exacerbate the perceived harm from exposure. A sense of guilt over giving children plastic toys, acknowledging the difficulty of ensuring safety was expressed. The recent acknowledgment that an old chair, which had been in the children’s bedroom for many years, was made with carcinogenic foam, was mentioned. Finally, some coping mechanisms were addressed. Some participants mentioned ignoring or downplaying risks to avoid constant worry, balancing awareness with an acceptance of the inevitability of exposure. One suggested that individuals can contribute by making informed choices. Another reflects on efforts to minimize exposure by being aware of purchases and food, though acknowledging the impossibility of avoiding all risks.

“Jag fick nyligen veta att en fåtölj jag har haft i mitt rum var gjord på skumgummi som var cancerframkallande. Så här, what? Och så säger mamma ja, men det finns ingen idé att vi slänger ut den för det är kvar i luften så att då får jag ha kvar min cancerfåtölj.” “Alltså, jag tänker på fåtöljen. Alltså, då känner jag inte mig så orolig. För att den har ändå gått igenom ganska mycket, så att den kanske är OK. Den kanske smittade någon annan innan den kom till mig.”

“I recently learned that an armchair I have had in my room was made of foam rubber that was carcinogenic. Like this, what? And then mom says yes, but there's no point in us throwing it out because it's still in the air so then I get to keep my cancer chair.” “So, I'm thinking about the armchair. So, then I don't feel so worried. Because it has gone through quite a lot anyway, so it might be OK. Maybe it infected someone else before it got to me.” [female, 18 years old]

During the last 10 years, at several municipalities in Sweden, there has been work going on to “detox” preschools and educate personnel about chemicals content and chemicals risks. Especially old items from a time when the chemicals legislation still allowed some flame retardants, phthalates and heavy metals, which are now regulated. One participant in one of the Swedish focus groups had been working at such a pre-school. She explained from a chemical audit at her workplace (a preschool), where common items were found to contain chemicals harmful to children, leading to extensive disposal of furniture and toys:

“Vi gjorde ju också en kartläggning på förskolan där jag jobbade, som, vi fick ju uppdraget att kartlägga allting som det var kemikalier i. Och då, (skratt) jättejobbigt, då fick vi slänga, liksom, som du sa, stolar och lego, alla de flesta grejer... vi inte ta emot några mera leksaker från föräldrar. Böcker, ingenting. För barn lägger allt i munnen, allting. Och då, och då tänkte vi; Men vad ska vi ha då här, för allting måste köpas nytt i så fall? Och ja, det var nya mattor, koppar...tallrikar, gardiner. Allt, nästan allting. Alltså kanske 60- 70 % av det som vi hade i förskolan. Det var vi tvungna att slänga. Böcker, allt möjligt, för att allting hade någonting som inte var bra för barnen. Och då, sen, tänkte vi ju, vad ska vi ha då? Får man gå till naturen då och så (skratt), leka i skogen kanske, eller så? Men det kostar ju också, och det är det som är problemet. Det kostar och det är det som hindrar, att, att vi, vi får ha de bra sakerna, eftersom de kostar, om vi ska vi köpa”

“We also did a survey at the preschool where I worked, ...we were given the task of surveying everything that had chemicals in it. And then, (laughter) really hard, then we had to throw away, like, as you said, chairs and Legos, all most stuff... we don't accept any more toys from parents. Books, nothing. Because children put everything in their mouth, everything. And then, and then we thought; But what should we have here, because everything has to be bought new in that case? And yes, there were new carpets, cups...plates, curtains. Everything, almost everything. So maybe 60-70% of what we had in preschool. We had to throw that away.

Books, anything, because everything had something that wasn't good for the kids. And then, later, we thought, what should we have then? Do you get to go to nature then (laughter), play in the forest, maybe, or something? But it also costs money, and that is the problem. It costs and that is what prevents us from having the good things, because they cost, if we are going to buy.” [female, 40 years old]

Information and literacy

In terms of information, it was stressed out the need for global research and cooperation to solve chemical exposure issues. Participants recommended focusing on chemicals that are less understood, expanding knowledge on commonly used substances and disseminating findings through accessible media like articles. Moreover, they were worried over the vast number of untested chemicals, highlighting the need for more safety research.

The importance of (scientifically based) trustful communication was highlighted. Some emphasized that people would care about chemicals if they understood the personal risks, advocating for impactful awareness campaigns. Additionally, the use of alternatives to harmful chemicals was recommended, helping the public make safer choices rather than attempting complete avoidance. Another highlighted topic was the need for reliable, accessible information sources to inform the public about chemical risks, without relying on second-hand information.

The necessity of having more collaboration between researchers and companies was mentioned and participants advocated for collaborative research projects between scientists and suppliers to develop feasible, mutually beneficial solutions that manufacturers will implement, emphasizing communication and practical knowledge exchange.

“... alla, alla ...måste snacka ju, snacka med varandra. Så att folk vet vad man håller på med så att man som kommer fram till en gemensam lösning. Så det inte blir så, liksom nåt sånt ställningskrig, att ja, nej, men sen så här: "Vi vill ju inte ha det där". Det måste... det måste ju vara en gemensam början. Eller, "Det här är problemet", eller "Det här är det som vi vill lösa". "Det här är så här". De måste liksom sätta sig ner och snacka om sådant. Forskarna måste ju se hur producenterna gör, hur det går till i praktiken. Vilka problem de har... Och, ja, producenterna måste gå och möta, möta forskarvärlden. Det måste komma, de måste vara i samma lag, typ.”

“...everyone or, as it were, must talk, talk to each other. So that people know what you are doing so that you arrive at a joint solution. So that it doesn't become like this, like some kind of positional war, that yes, no, but then like this: "We don't want that". It must... it must be a common beginning. Or, "This is the problem", or "This is what we want to solve". "This is like this". They kind of need to sit down and talk about such things. The researchers must see how the producers do it, how it works in practice. What problems they have... And, yes, the producers must go and face, face the scientific world. It must come, they have to be on the same team, like. [male, 55 years old]

Another topic of discussion was the need for more studies on long term effects based on the belief that short-term chemical exposure is regulated. An additional referred idea was the focus on the development of population-based studies, with people working in high-pollution areas to observe the real effects of chemical exposure.

Health consequences of exposure

Several health consequences of exposure were discussed, namely allergies, skin problems (e.g., eczema), respiratory diseases, cancer and fertility problems.

“Jag har problem med allergi, och så där, så jag använder inga... det är jättesvårt att hitta produkter som inte orsakar någonting överhuvudtaget, och jag fick prova fram en massa saker som har lovats att ha gått igenom astma- och och, vad heter de där, allergiförbundet, allt och ändå, liksom, det orsakade någonting i mig. Så jag tänker att någonstans måste man bara liksom acceptera för det går inte, tyvärr, att ta bort allt.”

"I have problems with allergies, and so on, so I don't use any... it's really hard to find products that don't cause anything at all, and I got to try a lot of things that have been promised to have gone through asthma- and and, what are they called, the allergy association, everything and yet, like, it caused something in me. So, I think that somewhere you just kind of have to accept because it's not possible, unfortunately, to remove everything."
[female, 40 years old]

Regulation

Overall, the global and regulatory responsibility theme has emerged with marked criticism of regulatory bodies like the EU for inadequate enforcement of environmental protection and uniform standards across nations. One participant talked about the buildup of industrial waste and contaminants in soil and water due to poorly regulated disposal, exemplified by specific cases in Sweden.

"Det finns oseriösa aktörer som kan agera. Eftersom ingen har koll liksom. Nu är det ju massor av ställen istället. Det är ju fullt med gifter i marken. Om vi tar Västerås, som exempel, betalar, var det 70 eller var det 100, 200 miljoner, för att rensa här utanför Skultuna? De kan skita i... Men de har bara lagt det där. Kostar hur mycket som helst. Och den där rättegången. Jo, det finns inga sådana ansvariga, de finns inte kvar längre. Så de kan inte betala det. Då får skattebetalarna ta det. Och det kostar ju resurser från andra håll, vanliga löntagare då."

"There are unscrupulous actors who can act. Because no one has any idea. Now there are lots of places instead. The ground is full of poison. If we take Västerås, as an example, pay was it 70 or was it 100, 200 million, to clear here outside Skultuna? They can screw up... But they just put it there. Costs any amount. And that trial. Well, there are no such people in charge, they don't exist anymore. So, they can't pay it. Then the taxpayers have to take it. And it costs resources from elsewhere, ordinary wage earners then." [male, 55 years old]

Individual protection strategies

Several individual protection strategies were presented. One example is to avoid unnecessary cleaning products. Also, it was noted that basic products like diluted soap may be as effective as specialized cleaning agents, containing more chemicals. The replacement of plastics with safer materials was another emergent idea. Other strategies included learning more about risks at early ages (for example, as early as at pre-school, as early education can instill lifelong habits of caution regarding chemicals), investing in organic farming and conscious consumption, choose items with environmental labels, read labels and avoid high exposure of specific chemicals.

"Till exempel om man sprejar. Det som man ser i reklam, där de säger att "Ja, använd det här för att ta bort smuts!" Det behövs inte! Bara att ta vatten och skrubba lite, för när du sprayar den där, den kommer till dig. Den där blir i luften. Man tror "oh, det är så gott det luktar." Men det är du som andas in de där kemikalierna. Ja, det är bara, det är bara att låtsas att det blir fint, men jag använder det inte. Jag använder bara vatten och ibland lite ättika. Och lite bikarbonat, liksom för vissa saker. För jag har liksom blivit medveten om det här, att, som jag sa, jag kan inte göra allt, men jag försöker göra i alla fall lite för min egen hälsa, för att hindra att man får cancer eller nån annan sjukdom."

"For example, if you spray. The thing you see in commercials, where they say "Yes, use this to remove dirt!" It is not necessary! Just take water and scrub a little bit, because when you spray it there, it comes to you. That one stays in the air. You think "oh, it smells so good." But you are the one breathing in those chemicals. Yeah, it's just, it's just pretending it's going to be nice, but I'm not using it. I just use water and sometimes a little vinegar. And some bicarbonate, like for some things. Because I've sort of become aware of this, that, as I said, I can't do everything, but I try to do at least a little for my own health, to prevent you from getting cancer or some other disease." [female, 40 years old]

Contexts of (increased) risk

Some environments can increase the risk of exposure. For example, industrial and occupational hazards were worth noticing, with concerns over workplace exposure, especially in industries with lax safety standards, as well as the role of imported products from countries with less stringent regulations. Environmental impact/contamination was also discussed, with expressions of worry about groundwater contamination in Sweden. There was also refer to the societal impacts. It was speculated that cheaper products might contain more chemicals and that using chemicals in food production to speed up processes and potentially lowering costs can increase chemical exposure.

"...jag är jätte bekymrad för grundvatten. Jag tänker, jag läser de där kartorna och de där rapporterna, och Oj, oj, oj, nu är det dåligt grundvatten och så, det tänker jag, att om vi inte tar hand om den råvaran då är vi verkligen illa ute."

"...I'm very concerned about groundwater. I think, I read those maps and those reports, and oh dear, now the groundwater is bad and so, I think that if we don't take care of that resource, we're really in trouble." [female, 61 years old]

Vulnerable groups

Children were seen as particularly vulnerable to the effects of chemicals, especially through food consumption. The participants expressed concern about the potential exposure of children to unsafe plastic toys, highlighting the difficulty in determining which products are truly safe. Additionally, they voiced worries about the use of second-hand furniture in childcare settings, which may contain harmful chemicals. The speaker recalls discarding old toys made of potentially unsafe plastics. In one of the focus groups, one participant had an experience with a chemical audit at her workplace (a preschool), where common items were found to contain chemicals harmful to children, leading to extensive disposal of furniture and toys. A project is now being performed in several municipalities in Sweden.

Examples of specific concerns about children's exposure include:

- The risk for preschool children, who often put objects in their mouths, necessitates strict regulations on chemical exposure in these settings.
- Small children are particularly sensitive to chemicals due to their developing bodies and lower resistance.
- Exposure duration matters, but children may be more affected by short-term exposure than adults.
- Teenagers may also be more susceptible to the effects of chemicals due to hormonal changes during puberty, such as increased levels of estrogen and testosterone, which can alter the body's response to chemical exposure.

Other vulnerable groups mentioned during the discussion were older individuals, passive smokers, who are exposed to secondhand smoke from others and face significant health risks, and individuals in low-income countries due to weaker regulations and lower awareness. This can occur when products are manufactured in these countries for export or when waste is exported to these regions. For instance, workers in these countries may be exposed to hazardous chemicals while working long hours for minimal pay, and the products they produce, such as clothing, may be exported to other countries.

Pathways of exposure

Two main pathways of everyday exposure were brought up. There was a belief that exposure to chemicals is inescapable in daily life (e.g., in air, water, and food). Plus, the general discomfort with chemicals in everyday items like food and clothing was discussed, emphasizing uncertainty about their effects. Notes how exposure occurs in many routine activities, like swimming, showering, cooking, or simply shopping.

Another pathway was related to how humans are polluting the natural environment, such as lakes and oceans, where animals also absorb pollutants. Specific sources such as fish from the Baltic Sea that may contain harmful chemicals, especially concerning children, were mentioned. A link with plastic contamination in oceans to food

safety concerns was made. Bioaccumulation of chemicals in humans and wildlife, particularly with food sources like fish and concerns about cumulative exposure over time was addressed.

Chemicals

In the focus groups, concerns about various chemicals that pose potential health risks were expressed. Antibiotics used in meat production, especially in imported meat, were one example. Petroleum products, commonly found in skincare products, flame retardants, used in various fabrics, asbestos, PFAS, and steroids, used for performance enhancement, were also mentioned. Some skepticism about the health benefits of "zero-sugar" products containing artificial sweeteners like stevia and aspartame was also raised. Finally, car exhaust was noted as a mixture of pollutants inhaled by individuals, that can also contribute to respiratory health problems.

"...det var ju mycket snack om sån här aspartam för något år sedan. Ja, då tänkte man ju, eller i alla fall jag, tänkte på det i en vecka, typ, och så slutade, typ, dricka Fanta-Zero, och så där. Men sen nästa vecka börjar man ju."

"...there was a lot of talk about this kind of aspartame a few years ago. Yes, then you thought, or at least I thought about it for a week, like, and then stopped, like, drinking Fanta-Zero, and so on. But then next week you start." [male, 22 years old]

3.5 Synthesis of the focus groups

Throughout the eight focus groups, several common themes have emerged, which are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Main themes emerging cross-sectionally in the hosted focus groups.

4. Citizen survey

Citizen surveys are a powerful tool for gathering public perspectives, knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors on specific topics. These surveys provide valuable insights into how citizens perceive issues of public interest, enabling policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders to better understand societal needs and expectations (OECD, 2017). By reaching a broad and diverse audience, citizen surveys ensure that the voices of the general population are included in decision-making processes, making policies and interventions more inclusive and effective (European Commission, 2021).

When addressing complex and often technical subjects, such as chemicals and their potential impacts on health and the environment, citizen surveys play a critical role. They help assess public awareness of chemical risks, gauge concerns related to exposure, and identify gaps in knowledge or communication (WHO, 2016b). These insights are essential for designing targeted outreach, educational campaigns, and evidence-based policies that resonate with the public (Rowe & Frewer, 2005).

The development of the PARC citizen survey was performed by a review of several previous studies, including Special Eurobarometer studies on topics such as attitudes toward the environment and chemical safety. These studies are mostly from the past decade, with examples including:

- International Social Survey Programme: Environment IV - ISSP 2020,
- Special Eurobarometer 456 - Chemical safety, 2016,
- Flash Eurobarometer 361 - Chemicals, 2012.

Furthermore, the questions from the non-representative citizen survey conducted within the framework of the HBM4EU project were taken into account.

The questionnaire for this citizen survey is designed to comprehensively capture various dimensions of the respondents' knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors regarding chemicals. The structure is organized into the following sections:

- personal information,
- questions on the environment,
- awareness and information about chemicals.

Through the questionnaire, among others, we assess the following aspects:

- the respondent's concern and opinion on environmental problems,
- the level of concern expressed by individuals regarding chemicals and their impacts,
- subjective and objective knowledge and beliefs about chemicals and associated risks,
- the willingness to act and pay for solutions, including environmentally conscious actions.

In addition to these core topics, the survey will allow for comparative analyses across countries, as well as differences based on gender, age, and socioeconomic status. Furthermore, the results will complement findings from focus group discussions by providing quantitative data on key themes, helping to explore patterns in risk perception.

The citizen survey is available in Appendix 5.

Online data collection will be conducted in 2025 among individuals aged 18–75 years by a subcontractor. The survey will be carried out in all PARC countries (Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Latvia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Slovakia, Slovenia, and the UK), except for Iceland due to its small population size. A total of 1,000 responses will be collected in each country, except for Luxembourg.

This sample size generally allows for reliable national-level insights. It is commonly used in large surveys conducted across Europe. Quota sampling will be applied, and the data will be representative of age, gender, type of settlement, and level of education. The National Hub Contact Points will provide the translation of the survey into national languages.

5. Conclusion

The first round of focus groups, conducted in four countries, provided valuable insights into citizens' perceptions and concerns regarding chemicals and related topics. The participating countries had the opportunity to enhance their skills in managing and analyzing focus groups. Preliminary results from the focus groups have already demonstrated their potential for immediate uptake to inform and shape communication strategies.

By exploring citizens' awareness, concerns, and information needs, the citizen survey will contribute to strengthening communication strategies within PARC and beyond.

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T3.2 – Communication, dissemination, and awareness

Focus groups training

January 29th, 2024

PARC

Agenda for the session

1. Principles of qualitative research approaches
2. Sampling guidelines
3. Script for the focus groups
4. Guidelines for conducting the focus groups
5. Guidelines for the transcription

PARC T3.2 — Focus group

Task 3.2: Communication, dissemination, and awareness

“Outreach activities are planned to raise awareness on risk assessment. Targeted surveys, focus groups and information campaigns, will be launched for different citizen groups (workers, professionals, and consumers) to collect new information of relevance to PARC and to gather more in-depth information about citizens’ needs and perception and concerns about PARC-related subjects”

PARC T3.2 — Focus group

Task 3.2: Communication, dissemination, and awareness

“Outreach activities are planned to raise awareness on risk assessment. Targeted surveys, focus groups and information campaigns, will be launched for different citizen groups (workers, professionals, and consumers) to collect new information of relevance to PARC and to gather more in-depth information about citizens’ needs and perception and concerns about PARC-related subjects”

Focus groups will be hosted in 20 countries (4 countries per year) between Y2 and Y6.

2 Focus groups should be hosted within each country.

Each hosting country will have 2 PMs.

The first 4 focus groups must be organized in Y2 (until the end of June 2024).

Timeline

Scientific research | types of knowledge

Phases of scientific theories (Dickoff et al, 1968)

Description of phenomenon

Uncovering relationships

Theory building up

Prediction & control

Association/ causality

Context of discovery/exploration

Context of confirmation

Dickoff, J., James, P. & Wiedenbach, E., 1968, 'Theory in a practice discipline, part 1: Practice oriented theory', Nursing Research 17(5), 415–435.

Paradigms in research designs

Kuhn, 1987

Quantitative & qualitative methods

	Qualitative	Quantitative
+ Used	In social and human sciences (soft)	In natural sciences(hard)
Goal	Description of realities	Testing hypotheses Identifying causal relationships
Design	Evolutionary; flexible	Structured, formal
Sampling	Small samples Purposive/intencional sampling	Random, representative Aims results generalization

Quantitative & qualitative methods

	Qualitative	Quantitative
Data collection	Open observation Non-structured interviews Document analysis <u>Focus groups</u>	Structured observation Structured interviews Questionnaires
Data type	Words	Numbers
Analysis	Inductive	Deductive (testing hypotheses)

Quantitative & qualitative methods

Typical aims of qualitative research

To study emerging, not well-known, phenomena

To learn about

- individuals' experiences

- beliefs, attitudes, stereotypes

- problem-solving processes

- narratives (ways of thinking/acting on) phenomena

- cultures/rituals

Hermeneutic principles

Interpretative research

Text / description of an action

Researcher

Reader

Hermeneutic research

Text / description of an action

Reader

Researcher

(co-understanding)

Phenomenological approach

Goal: “To explain the structure [...] of living experiences, searching [...] for the essence of a phenomenon” (Rose, Beeby & Parker, 1995)

Steps

Descriptive phenomenology (intuition → analysis → description)

Reductive phenomenology

Essence (“eidetic”) phenomenology

Data collection | Focus Group

Focus Group

“... is a carefully planned discussion designed to obtain perceptions on a defined area of interest in a permissive, non-threatening environment [...]

The discussion is comfortable and often enjoyable for participants as they share their ideas and perceptions. Group members influence each other by responding to ideas and comments in the discussion.”

(Krueger, 1994)

Focus groups — applications in research

Defining best characteristics associated to products/services

Production of scientific knowledge (self-contained research method)

Understanding results from quantitative studies

Development of research hypotheses

Building up of data collection instruments

Questionnaire architecture

Validation of questionnaires

Cultural adaptation of questionnaires

Focus groups - steps

1. Definition of goals
2. Development of the first version of the script (evolutive throughout the data collection)
3. Selection of participants characteristics (evolutive throughout the data collection)
4. Sampling (& sample size)
5. Conduction of focus groups
6. Transcription of focus groups
7. Content analysis
8. Report

Main goal of the PARC's T3.2 focus groups

To characterize citizens' perspectives and concerns about chemicals in daily used products (foods, clothes, cosmetics, ...)

Focus groups - steps

1. Definition of goals
2. Development of the first version of the script (evolutive throughout the data collection)
3. Selection of participants characteristics (evolutive throughout the data collection)
4. Sampling (& sample size)
5. Conduction of focus groups
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7. Content analysis
8. Report

Script (first version) of the focus group

Brief presentation of PARC (ppt still to be created → 15th February)

Sources of exposure (air, water, soil, products, food, ...)

Type of products that are of most concern

Substances of concern

Health concerns

Preferred sources of information about chemicals

Protective behaviours

Priority areas of research for PARC

Focus groups - steps

1. Definition of goals
2. Development of the first version of the script (evolutive throughout the data collection)
3. Selection of participants characteristics (evolutive throughout the data collection)
4. Sampling (& sample size)
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8. Report

Sampling

A dashed yellow oval is centered on the slide. Inside the oval, the text "Theoretical / intentional / criterion-based sampling" is written in a black, sans-serif font.

Theoretical / intentional /
criterion-based sampling

Sampling → which goals?

Sampling goal in quantitative approaches

Sampling goal in qualitative approaches

Not searching for consensus (or quantitative confirmation)... instead, we are looking for new ideas !

Sampling

Sampling regards...

- ... participants (sampling of cases)
- ... data for interpretation (internal sampling)
- ... reporting results (presentation sampling)

Sampling | results reporting (verbatim)

International Journal of
*Environmental Research
and Public Health*

Article

Chemical Exposure: European Citizens' Perspectives, Trust, and Concerns on Human Biomonitoring Initiatives, Information Needs, and Scientific Results

Maria Uhl ^{1,*}, Ricardo R. Santos ²

Some participants in another focus group identified the “chain of effects” of the human influence on the whole ecosystem:

“One of the one of the things that I think goes on in research that you do is you look at single chemicals. And one of the things that I think perhaps isn't looked at enough is the cocktail of chemicals that we're absorbing. Because we seem to have a lot more stuff that's going on. And the, it's actually how, how, what, what can be done about that, for example . . . ” (UK, female, part 1, lines 577–581).

“ . . . when you get in things that are coming in . . . outside the EU, for example, from South America, taking the example of grapes. What? How do we know they're not filled with pesticides?” (UK, female, part 1, lines 610–611).

Sampling participants

Sampling processes

Snowball

Typical cases

Rare/atypical cases

Exceptionally! : Random (with intentional and theoretically-based inclusion criteria)

Insightful / Verbal / Assertive participants

Recruitment

Direct invitation

Internet (forum/chat/facebook, ...)

Email-list

Sampling participants

Recruitment

Maximum variation principle (perspectives, knowledge, experiences, ...)

Similarity (age, gender, belonging group, hierarchy, ...)

Atypical cases AND Typical cases'

Continuous data comparison → evolutive sampling

Sample size

Data / theoretical saturation

Census (if applicable)

Inclusion criteria (for PARC T3.2 focus groups)

8-10 participants per focus group

- Adults (18+ years old)
- Gender (both)
- Level of education (with and without higher education degree)
- Living in urban vs rural setting
- Professional activity (diverse professions — white-collar workers, blue-collar workers, factory-setting workers, cosmetic-industry workers, agriculture workers, ...)
- Having children or not

Recruitment

Guidelines

Intergroups heterogeneity criteria | Intragroups homogeneity criteria (focus-group internal variation)

Number of focus groups : two per country

Duration: \cong 60 minutes

Size: 8 to 10 persons per focus group | inviting at least 10 (20% of dropouts)

Encouraging participation

Direct (phone / face-to-face) invitation (recall : one week before the focus group / day before)

Welcome coffee → sign of consent form

Gifts (at the end of the focus group)

Focus groups - steps

1. Definition of goals
2. Development of the first version of the script (evolutive throughout the data collection)
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8. Report

Setting of the focus group

Focus Group

Skills of moderator

Neutrality and objectivity

Train to “listen” and “hearing” and to interpret answers (active listening — it includes managing silence and other “non-verbal” behavior)

Train in qualitative research

Empathy

MIND THEORY

Active listening

Not an automatic process

Implies listening & reflecting (→ meta-listening)
Focused attention (verbal & non-verbal behavior)
Asking
Paraphrasing
Summarizing

Neutrality

Non-judgemental attitude
Not sharing own opinions or experiences

A focus groups is not a
therapeutic setting !!

Focus Group | coping with participants

The leader

The innovator

The group facilitator

The discrete

The explainer

The persuasive

The wanderer

The supporter

The distractor

The negotiator

The group divisor

The "moderator assistant"

Field notes

Descriptive material

Physical space/setting → Croqui (physical distribution of participants)

Participants (distinctive/relevant physical characteristics, participants' non-verbal relevant details, ...)

Group interaction (non-verbal)

Reflexive material

Insights, interpretation, hypothesis, ...

Focus groups - steps

1. Definition of goals
2. Development of the first version of the script (evolutive throughout the data collection)
3. Selection of participants characteristics (evolutive throughout the data collection)
4. Sampling (& sample size)
5. Conduction of focus groups
6. Transcription of focus groups
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8. Report

Transcription

Following the guidelines

(in: <https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/zotxgelt8acdh5617tha9/h?rlkey=utmik5uah7743678gugv6qlyt&dl=0>)

Transcribing & rechecking the transcription (ideally, a second researcher)

Focus groups | Transcription guidelines

There are several manuals of codes and rules for transcribing verbal data, depending on the type of qualitative approach used (e.g., narrative analysis, discourse analysis, grounded theory, interpretative phenomenological analysis).

For our study, and given our main goals, we will simplify the notation to be used, relying on the following rules:

- 1 Start by listening to the entire recording. This will give you an overall perspective of the text, which will then make it easier to transcribe.
- 2 The lines of text should be numbered. Go to the Layout tab and in the Page Setup group, click Line Numbers, as shown in the figure.

More info can be found [here](#).

- 3 Each entry of a participant should be preceded by a paragraph and a dash ("–"). Sometimes it is difficult to systematically identify the name of the participant. In these cases, the name is omitted, except for the moderator "M". Example:
 - hk kajd asda skjdh askjdh asdas dkajshd kajsdh asd
 - (M) - lkj lkj lkads alkdj alskdj asd askjdl askjd laskjd askcllasjd.

Ethical issues

Consent forms

Ethical submission (if applicable)

Ethical authorization (if applicable)

Focus Group

Data analysis

MAXQDA v. 24 (ideally)

IA summary & coding

Coder triangulation → at least two researchers

Looking for tendencies & patterns!

Evaluation of the training session

Please access the link:

<https://anketa.nijz.si/a/8b3e06a4>

Or follow the QR code:

T3.2 – Communication, dissemination, and awareness

Focus groups training

January 29th, 2024

PARC

T3.2 — Communication, dissemination, and awareness

Focus groups & Content Analysis

May 17th, 2024

PARC

PARC T3.2 — Focus group

Task 3.2: Communication, dissemination, and awareness

“Outreach activities are planned to raise awareness on risk assessment. Targeted surveys, focus groups and information campaigns, will be launched for different citizen groups (workers, professionals, and consumers) to collect new information of relevance to PARC and to gather more in-depth information about citizens’ needs and perception and concerns about PARC-related subjects”

PARC

Agenda for today

1. Focus group | roleplay
2. Content analysis

PARC

3

3

Questions addressed to us

Heterogeneity between participants | Have differences between participants or get a big number of people (example: 12 confirmations but some are quite similar and then just 8 turns up and those are the ones similar?)

Since we only have two focus groups per country, the ideal situation is to have the as much heterogeneity as we can. The ideal situation would be to try to maximize differences no matter how many participants are invited. So, even if some of them do not show up, we will have differences in the group.

Do we need to use the slides of PARC as suggested (for the focus group)?

The shared powerpoint was only an example that can be used and altered by each country

Should we use the script as shared? (Only topics? Or can we use specific questions?)

We use only guiding topics; but a more detailed script can be used, if needed

PARC

4

4

Script (first version) of the focus group

Brief presentation of PARC

Substances of concern

Type of products that are of most concern

Sources of exposure (air, water, soil, products, food, ...)

Substances of concern

Health concerns

Preferred sources of information about chemicals

Protective behaviours

Priority areas of research for PARC

PARC

5

5

Focus groups - steps

1. Definition of goals
2. Development of the first version of the script (evolutive throughout the data collection)
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6. Transcription of focus groups
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PARC

6

6

Setting of the focus group

7

Field notes

Descriptive material

Physical space/setting → Croqui (physical distribution of participants)

Participants (distinctive/relevant physical characteristics, participants' non-verbal relevant details, ...)

Group interaction (non-verbal)

Asamblea GP 24/11/2023
Grupo reunido en 3930, inicio de 09:26 a 10:14
Moderadores: Carolina Martínez y Valeria Aguado
Participantes: Susana Ponce, Sara Fernández, MC Ballester, Susana, Alida Patricia, Catalina Goss
Observadores: Lidia Pardo, Susana, Diego, Fabiana, Catalina

Orden de las sillas:
1° Catalina Goss - Susana
2° Susana - Sara Fernández
3° Sara Fernández - Fabiana
4° Sara Fernández - Catalina Goss
5° Alida Patricia - Alida Patricia
6° Alida Patricia - Alida Patricia
7° Susana Ponce - Catalina Goss (Catalina pedo-re ocupante silla)
8° Catalina Goss - Alida Patricia

Reflexive material

Insights, interpretation, hypothesis, ...

8

Questions addressed to us

Do field notes require anonymization? Should they be analyzed and shared?

The notes can include:

- major topics discussed that should not be missed in the content analysis
- non verbal behavior
- ideas discussed when 2 participants are talking at the same time and that could not be recorded properly

The notes taken by the co-moderator (or the third researcher in the room) should be analyzed, and only the content analysis will be shared. The same rules of pseudo-anonymization should be followed

PARC

9

Focus groups - steps

1. Definition of goals
2. Development of the first version of the script (evolutive throughout the data collection)
3. Selection of participants characteristics (evolutive throughout the data collection)
4. Sampling (& sample size)
5. Conduction of focus groups
6. Transcription of focus groups
7. Content analysis
8. Report

PARC

10

10

Transcription

Following the guidelines

(in: <https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/zotxgalt8acdh5617tha9/h?rlkey=utmik5uah7743678quqv6qlvt&dl=0>)

Transcribing & rechecking the transcription (ideally, a second researcher)

Focus groups | Transcription guidelines

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More info can be found [here](#).

3 Each entry of a participant should be preceded by a paragraph and a dash ["-"]. Sometimes it is difficult to systematically identify the name of the participant. In these cases, the name is omitted, except for the moderator "M". Example:

- M: hi kaji asda wqjth asqjth asdas dsajkhd kqjzth asd
 M: - hi kji kads akkj akkj asd asjgk asjgk asdskajp

Questions addressed to us

Tagging the interviewees in the transcripts

For the transcripts: F1.Participant1, F1.Participant2, F2.Participant1 should be used; we will need a table with the sociodemographic characterization of each participant

For the deliverable , we will use “Male, age, country, profession, etc.” after each citation

Questions addressed to us

Quotations

1. In the deliverable, we will only include the translated citations of parts of the transcriptions in the main text. No need to include the original transcripts, even if anonymized. As explained before, we will only need to indicate after each citation in the text that the citation belongs to, for example, a female, from Portugal, xx years old
2. In the scientific publication (when we agree on that), then we will also include translated citations but will also include the original transcripts, not translated in the appendixes.

PARC

13

Questions addressed to us

Sharing content analysis between partners?

The content analysis will be included in the deliverable. FMUL will be responsible for gathering the different analyses from the partners (in English).

FMUL will prepare the first version of the deliverable, based on the content analysis received from the partners. Then, a document (word) will be shared with the partners with a proposal and asking for edition/revision

PARC

14

Content analysis

MAXQDA v. 24 (ideally)

IA summary & coding

Coder triangulation → at least two researchers

Looking for tendencies & patterns!

Content analysis

Data corpus

All data collected for a particular project

Data item

All content from each of the focus groups

Data set

All data from the *corpus* that is used for a particular analysis

data extract

Individual coded chunk of data (verbatim)

Content analysis

“Thematic analysis is a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data”

Braun & Clark, 2006; 79

PARC

17

Content analysis | Steps

18

Content analysis | Steps

Table 1 Phases of thematic analysis

Phase	Description of the process
1. Familiarizing yourself with your data:	Transcribing data (if necessary), reading and re-reading the data, noting down initial ideas.
2. Generating initial codes:	Coding interesting features of the data in a systematic fashion across the entire data set, collating data relevant to each code.
3. Searching for themes:	Collating codes into potential themes, gathering all data relevant to each potential theme.
4. Reviewing themes:	Checking if the themes work in relation to the coded extracts (Level 1) and the entire data set (Level 2), generating a thematic 'map' of the analysis.
5. Defining and naming themes:	Ongoing analysis to refine the specifics of each theme, and the overall story the analysis tells, generating clear definitions and names for each theme.
6. Producing the report:	The final opportunity for analysis. Selection of vivid, compelling extract examples, final analysis of selected extracts, relating back of the analysis to the research question and literature, producing a scholarly report of the analysis.

www.QualResearchPsych.com Qualitative Research in Psychology 2006; 3: 77–101

Using thematic analysis in psychology

Virginia Braun¹ and Victoria Clarke²

¹University of Auckland and ²University of the West of England

Thematic analysis is a poorly demarcated, rarely acknowledged, yet widely used qualitative analytic method within psychology. In this paper, we argue that it offers an accessible and theoretically flexible approach to analysing qualitative data. We outline what thematic analysis is, locating it in relation to other qualitative analytic methods that search for themes or patterns, and in relation to different epistemological and ontological positions. We then provide clear guidelines to those wanting to start thematic analysis, or conduct it in a more deliberate and rigorous way, and consider potential pitfalls in conducting thematic analysis. Finally, we outline the disadvantages and advantages of thematic analysis. We conclude by advocating thematic analysis as a useful and flexible method for qualitative research in and beyond psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology* 2006; 3: 77–101

Key words: epistemology; flexibility; patterns; qualitative psychology; thematic analysis

Thematic analysis is a poorly demarcated, rarely acknowledged, yet widely used qualitative analytic method (Boyatzis, 1998; Roussin, 2001) within and beyond psychology. In this paper, we aim to fill what we, as researchers and teachers in qualitative psychology, have experienced as a current gap – the absence of a paper which adequately outlines the theory, application and evaluation of thematic analysis, and one which does so in a way accessible to students and those not particularly familiar with qualitative research. That is, we aim to write a paper that will be useful as both a teaching and research tool in qualitative psychology. Therefore, in this paper we discuss theory and method for thematic analysis, and clarify

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Content analysis | Steps

Table 2 A 15-point checklist of criteria for good thematic analysis

Process	No.	Criteria
Transcription	1	The data have been transcribed to an appropriate level of detail, and the transcripts have been checked against the tapes for 'accuracy'.
Coding	2	Each data item has been given equal attention in the coding process.
	3	Themes have not been generated from a few vivid examples (an anecdotal approach), but instead the coding process has been thorough, inclusive and comprehensive.
	4	All relevant extracts for all each theme have been collated.
	5	Themes have been checked against each other and back to the original data set.
Analysis	6	Themes are internally coherent, consistent, and distinctive.
	7	Data have been analysed – interpreted, made sense of – rather than just paraphrased or described.
	8	Analysis and data match each other – the extracts illustrate the analytic claims.
Overall	9	Analysis tells a convincing and well-organized story about the data and topic.
	10	A good balance between analytic narrative and illustrative extracts is provided.
	11	Enough time has been allocated to complete all phases of the analysis adequately, without rushing a phase or giving it a once-over-lightly.
Written report	12	The assumptions about, and specific approach to, thematic analysis are clearly explicated.
	13	There is a good fit between what you claim you do, and what you show you have done – ie, described method and reported analysis are consistent.
	14	The language and concepts used in the report are consistent with the epistemological position of the analysis.
	15	The researcher is positioned as <i>active</i> in the research process; themes do not just 'emerge'.

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Content analysis | Example of open coding

BOX 3.2 INITIAL CODING: LINE-BY-LINE CODING

Excerpt 1 *Christine Danforth, age 37, lupus erythematosus, Sjögren's syndrome, back injuries*

Lupus erythematosus is a systemic, inflammatory autoimmune disease of the connective tissue that affects vital organs as well as joints, muscles, and nerves. Sjögren's syndrome is a related autoimmune inflammatory disease characterized by dry mucous membranes of the eyes and mouth.

If you have lupus, I mean one day it's my liver; one day it's my joints; one day it's my head, and it's like people really think you're a hypochondriac if you keep complaining about different ailments ... It's like you don't want to say anything because people are going to start thinking, you know, 'God, don't go near her, all she is-is complaining about this.' And I think that's why I never say anything because I feel like everything I have is related one way or another to the lupus but most of the people don't know I have lupus, and even those that do are not going to believe that ten different ailments are the same thing. And I don't want anybody saying, you know, [that] they don't want to come around me because I complain.

Excerpt 2 *Joyce Marshall, age 60, minor heart condition, recent small CVA (stroke)*

In her case, the stroke left her with weakness, fatigue, and slowed responses when tired.

I have to see it [her CVA] as a warning. I can't let myself get so anxious. I have to live one day at a time.

I've been so worried about John [her husband who had had life-threatening heart attacks and lost his job three years before retirement] and preparing to get a job [her first in 38 years] ... It's just so hard with all this stress ... to concentrate on what I can do today. I always used to look to the future. I can't now; it upsets me too much. I have to live one day at a time now or else there may not be any me.

Shifting symptoms, having inconsistent days
 Interpreting images of self given by others
 Avoiding disclosure
 Predicting rejection
 Keeping others unaware
 Seeing symptoms as connected
 Having others unaware
 Anticipating disability
 Controlling others' views
 Avoiding stigma
 Assessing potential losses and risks of disclosing

Meaning of the CVA
 Feeling forced to live one day at a time

Having a worried past
 Earlier losses
 Difficulty in living one day at a time; concentrating on today
 Giving up future orientation
 Managing emotions through living one day at a time
 Reducing life-threatening risk

BOX 3.3 FOCUSED CODING

Excerpt 1 *Christine Danforth, age 37, lupus erythematosus, Sjögren's syndrome, back injuries*

If you have lupus, I mean one day it's my liver; one day it's my joints; one day it's my head, and it's like people really think you're a hypochondriac if you keep complaining about different ailments ... It's like you don't want to say anything because people are going to start thinking, you know, 'God, don't go near her, all she is-is complaining about this.' And I think that's why I never say anything because I feel like everything I have is related one way or another to the lupus but most of the people don't know I have lupus, and even those that do are not going to believe that ten different ailments are the same thing. And I don't want anybody saying, you know, [that] they don't want to come around me because I complain.

Excerpt 2 *Joyce Marshall, age 60, minor heart condition, recent small CVA (stroke)*

I have to see it [her CVA] as a warning. I can't let myself get so anxious. I have to live one day at a time.

I've been so worried about John [her husband who had had life-threatening heart attacks and lost his job three years before retirement] and preparing to get a job [her first in 38 years] ... It's just so hard with all this stress ... to concentrate on what I can do today. I always used to look to the future. I can't now; it upsets me too much. I have to live one day at a time now or else there may not be any me.

Avoiding disclosure

Assessing potential losses and risks of disclosing

Feeling forced to live one day at a time

Concentrating on today
 Giving up future orientation
 Managing emotions
 Reducing life-threatening risk

Charmaz K. Constructing Grounded Theory. Sage Publications. 2006

21

Content analysis | Example of axial coding

FIGURE 4.1 "Example of Clustering"

Charmaz K. Constructing Grounded Theory. Sage Publications. 2006

22

T3.2 — Communication, dissemination, and awareness

Focus groups training

May 17th, 2024

PARC

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

WP 3 • Task 3.2

Citizens' perspectives and concerns about chemicals

Focus groups – project plan

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

Co-funded by
the European Union

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

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1. GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT

1.1 Title

Citizens' perspectives and concerns about chemicals

1.2 Beginning date

January 2024

1.3 Duration

6 months

1.4 Responsible institution

Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade de Lisboa (FMUL)

1.5 Research team

The research team is made up of researchers who have the necessary skills and experience, both in the implementation of qualitative methods and in the substantive area (human biomonitoring, risk assessment), for the proper development of this study.

Researcher [Name]	Institution	Background

2. BACKGROUND OF THE PROJECT

Exposure to chemical substances with pathogenic potential is a constant result of contact with the multiplicity of environments to which we are exposed, including rural and urban environments, leisure, and work environments, as well as through the consumption of food, clothing, cosmetics, and water, among others.

Recognising the importance of monitoring the effect(s), both isolated and combined, of the multitude of potentially toxic chemical substances, a 7-year partnership under Horizon Europe was set – the PARC project: Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals – to improve knowledge about chemical substances to accelerate actions to better protect human health and the environment.

The PARC programme has three main objectives:

1. Develop the scientific skills needed to address current and future challenges in chemical safety
2. Provide new data, methods and innovative tools to those responsible for assessing and managing the risks of chemical exposure
3. Strengthen the networks which bring together actors specialised in the different scientific fields contributing to risk assessment

A key objective of PARC is to promote European cooperation, advance research, increase knowledge of chemical risk assessment and train relevant methodological skills. The results will help launch European and national strategies to reduce risks posed by hazardous chemicals to health and the environment. Further on they will help to reduce animal testing and implement strategies for next-generation risk assessment.

As multinational European project, PARC involves close to 200 institutions working in the areas of the environment or public health from 28 countries and three EU authorities, including the European Chemical Agency (ECHA), the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), and the European Environment Agency (EEA). The partnership is coordinated by ANSES, the French Agency for Food Safety, Environmental Protection and Occupational Health, and has the Lisbon School of Medicine as partner.

From science to the society

The PARC partnership has as its main goal to boost research and innovation in support of chemical risk assessment, aiming in particular to: better anticipate emerging risks, better account for combined risks, and underpin the concrete implementation of new orientations in European public policies to safeguard health and the environment in response to important issues for health, the ecology and citizens' expectations. The research strategy and work programme will ensure an open and transparent dialogue between scientific and regulatory bodies is promoted, involving all stakeholders.

In view of this context, it has been widely acknowledged that the adoption of a two-way risk communication strategy focused on participation and cooperation between stakeholders (scientists, policymakers, and citizens) is crucial. Indeed, risk perception is influenced by several factors and not only a result of information deficit (personal experience, environmental consciousness, related knowledge, media coverage, communication strategy, and source information credibility).

3. THE STUDY

As part of the Work Package 3 – Synergies, collaborations and awareness, Task 3.2 Communication, dissemination, and, the aim of this study is to characterize European citizens' perspectives and concerns about chemicals in daily used products (foods, clothes, cosmetics, ...). The ultimate aim of this information gathering is that it can be used to define the scientific agenda in the area of chemical risk assessment, but also to define health policies, with a view to the safe management of chemical substances and the protection of human health in Europe.

As part of the PARC project, the Programme's Management and Coordination Boards selected 20 European countries to undertake the same study locally. This research protocol concerns the study to be carried out in Portugal.

4. METHODS

To gain a comprehensive and triangulated understanding of Portuguese citizens' perceptions of chemical exposure and to achieve the study's objectives, a qualitative approach was adopted, with the study design following the principles of Grounded Theory and data collection through focus groups.

4.1 Focus group

The focus group is a qualitative data collection method that allows for a structured discussion involving the sharing and clarification of the participants' points of view and ideas. It is a data collection technique that involves situations of social interaction, with a small number of people, in a context of discussion on a specific, well-defined topic, with the aim of collecting qualitative data (i.e. verbal and relational) through "focussed" discussion.

For this study, a focus group will be conducted by a team (a moderator and a co-moderator) with experience in the technique. The focus group will be conducted in a semi-structured format, with open questions being asked of the participants according to a previously defined script, to promote a wide-ranging discussion, but limited to the topics in question and without detracting from the objectives of the study. In addition, since focus groups are being held in other consortium countries, the intention is to follow a similar structure in all countries.

Given the resources allocated to this component of the study, only two focus group per country is planned. The focus group will include 10 Portuguese citizens (13 people will be invited, with an estimated 25 percent not participating). In this sense, the main criterion for intra-group homogeneity is residence in the country where the focus group is being held. The criteria for intra-group heterogeneity are: gender, age groups (18 to 64), educational level, geographical area, professional activity and having children or not. Given the objective of characterising the perspectives on chemicals of citizens without responsibilities or formal education in this area of knowledge, the main exclusion criteria are: working with chemicals, being a doctor, veterinary doctor, nurse, nutritionist, biologist, chemist, physicist, or from another area that implies knowledge related to chemicals, risk assessment or human biomonitoring. Other exclusion criteria are: not mastering or for some reason having difficulty expressing themselves orally in Portuguese, and refusing to sign the informed consent document.

Participants will be recruited to take part in the focus groups through different ways, namely online posts on institutional homepages or social media accounts of the hosting institution, or advertisements posted in public/community buildings within the adjacent geographical area of the focus group venue. Also, when possible, individuals from former surveys or qualitative studies who explicitly informed to be available to be invited to participate in further observational studies will be contacted. Volunteers willing to participate will be acknowledged through a short electronic form, where they will be asked to indicate their willingness to participate in the focus groups and provide preferred details of contact (e.g., e-mail, telephone number), after reading and confirming acceptance of an informed consent form. All the procedures relating to the focus group (main goals of the PARC project and the focus groups, structure of the focus groups, voluntary participation, data protection measures, research-team contacts for further information, and ways of future access to research results) will be explained in the informed consent form. A researcher from the team will be responsible for the contacts to validate the participation.

The focus group will be held in one of FMUL's rooms. The space will have to guarantee acoustic conditions that allow for adequate recording of the verbal content and will have to allow for changes in the seating arrangement. The focus group will last approximately 90 minutes and the verbalised content will be recorded on audio for later transcription and content analysis.

The audio content will be transcribed (according to predefined standards in the manual) and anonymised. Its content will then be analysed collaboratively by two researchers from the social sciences, ensuring triangulation of perspectives, using qualitative data analysis software (MAXQDA, version 2024).

Those invited to the focus group will receive an informed consent document in advance (explaining the objectives and procedures of the study) and their confirmation of participation will be made only after signing it. Participation will be strictly voluntary (at all times) and the researchers will guarantee the confidentiality of the recorded content, which will be analysed as a group.

4.2 Ethical considerations

The rights of the participants will be safeguarded and in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. The legal legislation in force will also be respected and the necessary confidentiality of the personal information collected will be ensured.

Participation in the study is voluntary and only individuals over the age of 17 who have read and agreed to (by signing) the informed consent document will be included. The informed consent document will contain the necessary information (in terms of project description, objectives, and risks and benefits for the participant), guarantee of confidentiality, form of use and data security, so that the participant can make an informed decision about whether or not to take part in the study.

Potential participants are recognised as having the right to refuse or cancel their participation in the study at any time, and have the right to maintain their privacy, as well as access to all the information they need and the data that will be collected on them.

FOCUS GROUPS PROJECT PLAN

The database will be used exclusively by the research team responsible. The database with the sociodemographic information of the participants and the transcripts will be kept in an encrypted, password-protected file known to the **FMUL** research team. It will only be shared with the team coordinating PARC Task 3.2 and in an anonymised format.

The maximum data retention period will be 7 years, which will be kept at **FMUL** and then destroyed. The project's researchers assume full responsibility for the confidentiality of the data collected.

The data is the property of the Lisbon School of Medicine, which is responsible for sharing it with the partners of the PARC Project mentioned above, while guaranteeing that it is shared in an encrypted and anonymised file.

Focus groups | Transcription guidelines

Oswaldo Santos & Ana Virgolino

There are several manuals of codes and rules for transcribing verbal data, depending on the type of qualitative approach used (e.g., narrative analysis, discourse analysis, grounded theory, interpretative phenomenological analysis).

For our study, and given our main goals, we will simplify the notation to be used, relying on the following rules:

- 1 | Start by listening to the entire recording. This will give you an overall perspective of the text, which will then make it easier to transcribe.
- 2 | The lines of text should be numbered. Go to the Layout tab and in the Page Setup group, click Line Numbers, as shown in the figure.

More info can be found [here](#).

- 3 | Each entry of a participant should be preceded by a paragraph and two dots (":"). Sometimes it is difficult to systematically identify the name of the participant. In these cases, the name is omitted and substituted by Unknown, except for the moderator. Example:

Ana: hk kajd asda skjdh askjdh asdas dkajshd kajsdh asd

Moderator: lkj lkj lkads alkdj alskdj asd askjdl askjd laskjd askdlasjd.

Unknown: z nz,vmnzxv znxmv, zmxvz vio evhoiewhv ew vhwewoiwe wvhoih
oiewvhweiovh ewiohvev owiehv ewvwevoihew vioweh voiewhv ewiovh
ewoivh ewv.

Vweh vweohv oewivh weivhw evhweiovh oweihv ehviewhv weihv.

Asd askdj askdj askdja sd asjkdaksjd asdj askld jlaskjd laskjd asdj askdj
askl haskjdh akjsdh.

- 4** | Simultaneous interventions (e.g., by two participants), which are understandable in the recording, should be recorded.

Example: a participant is speaking and, in the middle of their speech, another participant makes a comment at the same time (understandable on the recording), without interrupting the first participant's speech:

Ana: czx xkjcxc kjzhxckjh zxc zxhkczyjh cxzkljh zxc dsfbcvsdalkchasdlc ew
cwuiecg asdlc gsdlcjhg acas cghjsd cgsdvcds vasd vglajhsdgvasd
gasdlvjghasldhgvewriu r eviasugv asdlvi asdvl advsgiagsdv asdv...

(Osvaldo: zxcz czx czxkljc hzxkljhc zklxjczx czxkljch)

Cz xczx chkjzch zxc zxkjch zxc hzxkjhc zxkjhc zxkcoj zx chzxj kclzxjhc zx
cjhzkx lcjhzx czx hcjzklxjch zxcj

- 5** | Simultaneous reactions by several members of the group, making the recording imperceptible (collective agitation), should be recorded with the agitation time indicated in numbers and square brackets.

Example 1: the participant's speech is interrupted for approximately 15 seconds by agitation from several members of the group (i.e. several voices simultaneously) and then the same participant resumes speaking:

Ana: df adsfh kasdjfh sdfasd hfkjsdhf [15''] zxc czxkjch zxkjh c

Example 2: the participant's speech is interrupted for approximately 15 seconds by a collective uproar, after which another participant continues:

Ana: df adsfh kasdjfh sdfasd hfkjsdhf

[15'']

Oswaldo: df adsfh kasdjfh sdfasd hfkjsdhf

6

When a participant speaks/intervenes for the first time (not counting the introduction speech, when providing name, age, occupation, ...) after a long time (i.e., more than 20 minutes), it is necessary to indicate the recording time (in minutes) in which this participation takes place:

Ana: (25') (1st) ddsad ad alkdj asd alksdj alksdj aslkdj askljdh asda sd ashjd askjd hlaskj das das dlkjha slkdjh askdasd asjkd haslkjdh alksjdh asd sahjkdasdh.

Sadas dhajsk dalskjdh asd ahsjkd lasjdh asda skdj haskjdh askjdh asdasd hasj kdhasljdh aslkjdh asdashjdkashd asdkasd.

7

The transcription must be comprehensive, which includes the notation of silences and "(ha)" or "(hum hum)". The way to indicate silence is with inverted square brackets, concerning the duration of the silence. Example of a 15-second silence and a few "hã":

Ana: shjh hjsk hjd (...hã...) asd askjdh akjsdh (...hã...) asd ahjskd halksjdh askljdh askljdh (...hã...) asd ashjk dhlaksjdh (...hã...) asd hasjkd lasjdh asdhjkasjdh as.

]15"[

Ovaldo: sadas dhajsk (...hã...) dhasd aslkdjhasd (...hã...) ashjkd lasjdh askljdh askljdasd hasjkd lkasjdh askjdh asd.

8 | Laughter should be indicated in square brackets.

Example 1:

Ana: df adsfh kasdjfh sdfasd hfkjsdhf [laughter from Ana] zxc czxkjch zxkjh c.

Example 2:

Ana: df adsfh kasdjfh sdfasd hfkjsdhf [laughter from Ovaldo] zxc czxkjch zxkjh c

Example 3:

Ana: df adsfh kasdjfh sdfasd hfkjsdhf [laughter from several participants] zxc czxkjch zxkjh c

9 | Hesitations in speech (e.g. brief interruptions, typical of reflection or attempts at recall) are indicated with ellipsis in curly brackets:

Ana: sa dhasd asd (...) ad ksajhdasaskjdh (...) das hdka sdsdkjhas da skjdh asdahjksdh.

- 10 | Speech with an elevated tone (i.e. emotional speech) is indicated with an upward arrow in brackets (all in bold):

Ana: h sds djkfh skjdfh sdfsd sckfjh (↑)

- 11 | Transcriber's notes on the content of the recording can be included if they are in square brackets, italicized, and underlined.

Example 1:

Ana: sdad askjd hasd askjdh asda shdjaks dhaskjdh asdalskdjhas dha sjdh ajkh ksdjhasdaskdjh as.

[The participant sitting to the left of the latter expressed non-verbal disagreement with the statement]

Example 2:

- sadas kdjash daskd ashdkjash d *[while speaking, this participant keeps his gaze on the participant sitting to his left]* ds fsdf lsdkjf sdf sdlkfj sdlkfj sdfsd fskdj f.

SURVEY

FINAL VERSION

Citizen survey

P-A-R-C Year 3

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

Co-funded by
the European Union

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

Make your opinion count for safer management of chemicals in Europe

Please take part in a short citizen survey on the environment and chemicals

In our daily lives, we are exposed to chemicals that are widely used in different products. The assessment of potential risks of chemicals that are used in the production of products is very important to protect individual and public health.

Since everyone may be exposed to chemicals through the food we eat, the air we breathe, and the products we use, we would like to know more about what EU citizens think about chemicals, as well as what your needs and concerns are on this topic.

Therefore, we would like to invite you to answer this short questionnaire that will take you approximately 20 minutes. By answering the following questions, you will help us to better answer the needs of the European citizens.

Your response will be anonymous and will be treated confidentially according to the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The anonymized data will be processed by the research partners of PARC (Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals) and the results of the survey will be published online at <https://www.eu-parc.eu> in 2026.

If you decide to withdraw your participation, you may choose to do so at any time, without any consequences.

Thank you!

PERSONAL INFORMATION

1. You are:

- male
- female
- prefer not to answer

2. How old are you?

----- years

3. Where were you born?

Please select from the list

Austria

Belgium

Croatia

Cyprus

Czech Republic

Denmark

Estonia

Finland

France

Germany

Greece

Hungary

Iceland

Ireland

Israel

Italy

Latvia

Lithuania

Luxembourg

Netherlands
Norway
Poland
Portugal
Slovakia
Slovenia
Spain
Sweden
Switzerland
United Kingdom
In other country. *[Which one?]*

Extra information: In which country do you live? *(it will be supplied by the contractor)*

Please select from the list

Austria
Belgium
Croatia
Cyprus
Czech Republic
Denmark
Estonia
Finland
France
Germany
Greece
Hungary
Iceland
Ireland
Israel
Italy
Latvia

Lithuania
Luxembourg
Netherlands
Norway
Poland
Portugal
Slovakia
Slovenia
Spain
Sweden
Switzerland
United Kingdom

4. Since what age have you lived in the country you currently live in now?

Please select from the list

6. Please indicate the approximate number of inhabitants of the city/town you reside in.

- less than 5.000 inhabitants
- 5.001 to 20.000 inhabitants
- 20.001 to 100.000 inhabitants
- 100.001 to 500.000 inhabitants
- more than 500.000 inhabitants
- I don't know

7. What is your highest level of education (concluded)?

- ISCED 0: Early childhood education
- ISCED 1: Primary education
- ISCED 2: Lower secondary education

- ISCED 3: Upper secondary education
- ISCED 4: Post-secondary non-tertiary education
- ISCED 5: Short-cycle tertiary education
- ISCED 6: Bachelor's degree or equivalent level
- ISCED 7: Master's degree or equivalent level
- ISCED 8: Doctoral degree or equivalent level

9. What is your level of education in natural science (chemistry, physics and biology)?

- I have no science education.
- I received science education at school (not university studies).
- I have a university degree (or equivalent) in the field of science education.

8. What is your current main employment status?

- professional active (either dependent or independent)
- student
- housemaker
- pensioner/retired
- unemployed/ looking for a job
- other, please specify -----

10. Have you got any children?

- yes
- no

11. How would you assess your family's financial situation/standard of living?

- excellent
- good
- average
- below average

- very bad

In case of very bad:

12. Do you receive social welfare?

- yes
- no

QUESTIONS ON THE ENVIRONMENT

13. From the following list, please pick the issues that you feel are the most important for your country of residence today. You can choose maximum three issues.

- Health care
- Education
- Crime
- The environment — (environmental protection/healthy environment/including chemical exposure)
- Immigration/emigration
- The economy
- Terrorism
- Poverty
- None of these
- Can't choose

14. Generally speaking, how concerned are you about environmental issues?

Please tick one box below to indicate what you think, where 1 means you are not at all concerned and 5 means you are very concerned.

1	2	3	4	5
Not at all concerned	Slightly concerned	Somewhat concerned	Concerned	Very concerned

15. Here is a list of some different environmental and/or human health issues.

Which problems, if any, do you think are the 3 most important for your country as a whole?

Priority No. 1, Priority No. 2, Priority No. 3

- Air pollution
- Chemicals in food
- Chemicals in other products
- Water shortage

- Floodings
- Water pollution
- Nuclear waste
- Domestic waste disposal
- Soil pollution
- Microplastics in ocean
- Rise of temperature of oceans' water
- Heat waves
- Genetically modified foods
- Acidification of oceans
- Scarcity of natural resources
- Biodiversity loss
- None of these
- Can't choose

16. How much do you agree or disagree with each of these statements?

Please tick one box on each line

Strongly agree, Agree, Neither agree nor disagree, Disagree, Strongly disagree, Can't choose

- Modern science will solve our environmental problems with little change to our way of life.
- We worry too much about the future of the environment and not enough about prices and jobs today.
- Almost everything we do in modern life harms the environment.
- People worry too much about human progress harming the environment.
- In order to protect the environment, [COUNTRY] needs economic growth.
- Economic growth always harms the environment.

17. How willing would you be to pay much higher prices/taxes in order to protect the environment?

- Very willing
- Fairly willing
- Neither willing nor unwilling
- Fairly unwilling
- Very unwilling
- Can't choose

18. Which of the following approaches do you think would be the best way of getting business and industry in your country to protect the environment and - at the same time - your health?

Please tick one box only

- Heavy fines for businesses that damage the environment and/or human health.
- Use the tax system to reward businesses that protect the environment and/or human health.
- More information and education for businesses about the advantages of protecting the environment and/or human health.
- Can't choose.

19. Which of the following approaches do you think would be the best way of getting people and their families in your country to protect the environment?

Please tick one box only

- Heavy fines for people who damage the environment.
- Use the tax system to reward people who protect the environment.
- More information and education for people about the advantages of protecting the environment.
- Can't choose.

20. How often do you avoid buying certain products for environmental reasons?

- Always
- Often

- Sometimes
- Never

21. How often do you avoid buying certain products to reduce your exposure to chemicals?

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Never

22. In the last five years, have you ...

Please tick one box on each line (Yes, No)

- ... signed a petition about an environmental issue?
- ... given money to an environmental group?
- ... joined any group focusing on environmental protection?
- ... taken part in a protest or demonstration about an environmental issue?

AWARENESS AND INFORMATION ABOUT CHEMICALS

23. In general, would you say that you are concerned about being exposed to hazardous chemicals in your daily life?

- Yes, very much
- Yes, a little
- No, not really
- No, not at all
- Don't know

24. Do you think that you can find chemical substances in the following...?

1. No, definitely not
2. No, probably not
3. Yes, probably
4. Yes, definitely
5. Don't know

- Food and drinks
- Clothes and shoes
- Electronic appliances
- Children's toys
- Cosmetics or beauty products
- Cleaning products
- Paint
- Furniture
- The ambient air

25. How informed do you feel about the potential dangers of the chemicals contained in products such as food, paints, detergents, household products, clothes, furniture, electronics, toys and cosmetics?

- Very well informed

- Rather well informed
- Not very well informed
- Not informed at all
- Don't know

26. Do you think that the products containing chemicals that you can buy in your country are safe for human health and for the environment?

- No, not at all
- No, not really
- Yes, to some extent
- Yes, completely
- Don't know

27. In order to protect human health and the environment from hazardous chemicals, do you think that the current level of regulation and standards as implemented in the EU is...

- sufficiently high and could even be lower
- at the right level and should not be lowered or increased
- not high enough and should be increased
- Don't know

28. Where do you generally find information about the potential dangers of chemicals contained in household products, clothes, furniture, electronics and cosmetics? Please rank the following options in order of relevance.

- on the product labels
- in the media (newspapers, magazines, TV, radio, online social media and Internet)
- through NGOs or consumer organisations
- through public authorities
- through companies that produce or sell these products (e.g. communication campaigns, websites, publications)

- through family, friends or relatives
- I never look for this information
- Don't know

29. Imagine that you are interested in a newly launched product containing new chemicals. Which of the following statements best describes what you would do?

Please tick one box only

- You would assume it is considered safe and buy it immediately.
- You would buy it shortly after release, as long as you had heard nothing about possible adverse effects.
- You would buy it only after searching and finding sufficient information on its functionality and safety.
- You would wait until the product had been proven to be working and safe over a long period of time
- You would never buy it

30. Which of the following products do you or would you check the ingredients or composition of before purchasing — for example for health reasons or to protect the environment?

(Multiple answers possible)

- Food and drinks
- Clothes and shoes
- Electronic appliances
- Children's toys
- Cosmetics or beauty products
- Cleaning products
- Paint
- Furniture

- Other, please specify -----

31. Do you agree or not with each of the following statements?

1. Strongly disagree
 2. Tend to disagree
 3. Tend to agree
 4. Strongly agree
- It is possible to completely eliminate dangerous chemical substances from our daily life.
 - New chemical substances can help in reducing the use of natural resources.
 - New chemical substances can contribute to a better environment.
 - New chemical substances are involved in most industrial innovations.
 - In the EU, any product containing new chemical substances have been properly tested.
 - The number of chemicals in the outdoor environment has decreased in the last decades.
 - Exposure to chemicals has decreased in the last decades.
 - With regard to health, the main issue is not to what extent you are exposed to a dangerous chemical substance, but whether or not you are exposed to it at all.
 - If a person is exposed to an extremely small amount of a chemical that is harmful at larger amounts, then that person will probably be seriously ill some day in the future, even if the amount is extremely small.
 - Exposure to multiple chemicals (mixtures) may influence their potential health consequences.
 - I am concerned about the health effects from a chemical mixture (cocktail effects).

32. From the following list, please choose up to three issues that concern you the most regarding chemical exposure.

Priority No. 1, Priority No. 2, Priority No. 3

- industrial emissions
- road traffic
- pesticides in the environment
- environmental tobacco smoke
- chemical contaminants in drinking water
- chemicals in building materials
- chemicals in consumer products
- chemicals in personal care products (e.g. cosmetics, shampoo, shaving cream)
- pharmaceuticals
- psychoactive substances (e.g. tobacco, drugs)
- pesticides in food
- contaminants in food (e.g. mercury, cadmium, dioxins, mycotoxins)
- food additives, flavouring
- contaminants from food contact materials (e.g. plasticizers and heavy metals from food packaging, kitchenware and tableware)
- chemical substances at the workplace

33. We can be exposed to a chemical compound in many ways. In your opinion, which of the following exposure sources are particularly dangerous?

No danger / limited danger / moderately dangerous / extremely dangerous

- outdoor environment (e.g. soil, water, air)
- the home environment (e.g. dust, indoor air)
- the workplace
- food
- food packaging
- drinking water
- psychoactive substances (e.g. tobacco, drugs)
- pharmaceuticals
- household products (e.g. cleaning products, paints, arts and craft supplies)
- non-food consumer products (e.g. textiles, shoes, sport and office items)

- personal care products (e.g. cosmetics, shampoo, shaving cream)
- toys
- other source(s)

34. Chemicals enter the body through different exposure routes. Please rank them based on their importance.

Priority No. 1, Priority No. 2, Priority No. 3

- inhalation
- ingestion
- dermal uptake

35. The level of exposure to hazardous chemicals can be reduced by... Which of these do you think is /would be the most important/most effective in your country? Please rank them in order of importance.

Priority No. 1, Priority No. 2, Priority No. 3,

- improving emission controls of industrial activities
- improving control measures in terms of food and product safety
- ensuring better control of compliance with existing regulation of chemicals by industries
- improving control of imported products
- promoting campaigns to reduce personal exposure to hazardous substances
- improving our understanding of human exposure to chemicals and their possible effects on health
- informing the public on their exposure to chemicals
- informing the public on the potential health consequences of chemical exposure in order to change consumer behaviour
- Informing the public on their exposure to combinations of chemicals (mixtures) and the potential health consequences
- Informing workers on their exposure to chemical substances in the workplace environment

36. The following statements focus on the risk assessment of chemicals conducted by scientists.

Please indicate which of these statements you think is true.

Please only indicate 'Don't know' if you really don't know.

- Scientists never assess the risk of one substance at a time and always assess the risks of several chemicals combined.
- Scientists usually assess the risk of one substance at a time and rarely assess the risks of several chemical combined.
- Scientists always assess the risk of one substance at a time and never assess the risks of several chemicals combined.
- Don't know.

37. PARC is a 7-years partnership co-funded by the European Union, which aims to develop next-generation chemical risk assessment to protect human health and the environment. A key objective of PARC is to promote European cooperation, share knowledge, advance research, increase knowledge of chemical risk assessment and train relevant methodological skills. By doing so, it supports the European Union's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, paving the way for the "Zero pollution" ambition announced in the European Green Deal. How do you think zero chemical pollution can be achieved, if at all?